

A DSL for Monadic Decision Problems, Responsibility under Uncertainty and Tipping Point Notions

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Abstract

We develop a domain-specific language (DSL) for the specification of decision problems in the context of tipping point research, on top of a lightweight version the generic Botta et al. 2017 framework for specifying and solving monadic sequential decision problems. The aim is to improve accountability in the context of climate policy advice by narrowing the gap between mathematical problem specification and implementation. This is achieved by using a programming language based on Dependent Type Theory, in which it is possible to express specification, implementation and proof that the implementation fulfils certain properties within the same language.

We extend the Botta et al. theory with generic measures of responsibility and a syntax to transparently express goals of decision making. The usage of the framework is illustrated by the specification of a conceptual stochastic greenhouse gas emission problem. In a further extension of the basic theory, we show the correctness of the generic backward induction algorithm implemented in the framework in a more general setting than commonly considered in control theory.

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1 Introduction

We develop a domain-specific language (DSL) for the specification of decision problems in the context of tipping point research based on earlier work on a computational theory of policy advice proposed by Botta et al. in [BJI17a]. Our aim is to improve accountability in the context of climate policy advice by narrowing the gap between mathematical problem specification and implementation [BBCMM22b, BBCMM21, BBCMM22a] This is achieved by using a programming language based on Dependent Type Theory, in which it is possible to express specification, implementation and proof that the implementation fulfils certain properties within the same language.

As basis for the further work presented in this report, we define a lightweight version of the [BJI17a] theory that is easier to use in practice and yet sufficiently expressive. We extend the Botta et al. theory with generic measures of responsibility and a syntax to transparently express goals of decision making. The usage of the framework is illustrated by the specification of a conceptual stochastic climate policy problem. In the example we also discuss how to make use of conditional probabilities in the spirit of Bayesian belief networks to define transition function of stochastic decision problems in a modular way.

In a further extension of the basic theory, we discuss what correctness means for the generic backward induction algorithm of the theory and show under which conditions it computes provably optimal policy sequences. This allows to use this algorithm in a more general setting than commonly considered in control theory. This is crucial if non-standard combinations of measures and non-determinism, beyond the expected value measure and ordinary stochastic problems are considered.

In this report we primarily summarise our work presented in [BB21, BBC⁺21] including some small extensions, and give pointers to possible future work. Together with [BBCMM22c] it forms Deliverable 6.2 of the [EU Horizon 2020 Project TiPES](#) [TiP23]. As a supplement, the slides of several introductory talks on the material covered in this report and the underlying paradigm are available online [Bot20a, Bot20b, Bot20c, Bre20, MMB20, Bot21, Bre21, Bot22, Bre22].

Technical remarks. The theory used in the report is heavily based on dependent types and is formulated in the programming language *Idris* [Bra17, The10]. Public versions in Idris are available in [B⁺21] and [B⁺22]. For introductions to functional programming and dependent types, see [Bir14, Bra17]. An introductory course on formal specification, monadic dynamical systems and the IdrisLibs framework of [BJI17a] is available as TiPES deliverable D6.1 [BBCMM20]. The report itself has been generated via `lhs2TEX`[HL15] from literate Idris files. These are publicly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6826927> and can be type-checked for correctness.

2 Framework

In this section, we give a summary of the theory for the specifying and solving of *finite horizon sequential decision problems (SDPs)* which is used in [BB21] and [BBC⁺21]. This theory is a lightweight version of the framework of Botta, Jansson and Ionescu presented in [BJI17a] which has been developed in TiPES, trading to a certain degree expressivity against ease of use. Here we recap the lightweight theory and briefly discuss the differences between the two theories in Subsection 2.2. Longer introductions to monadic sequential decision problems and the respective versions of the framework can be found in [BJI17a, BB21, BBC⁺21].

2.1 Problem specification and solution

In a nutshell, the theory consists of two sets of components: one for the *specification* of sequential decision problems (SDPs) and one for their *solution* with verified backward induction. For informal introductions to SDPs, see [BJI17a]. Reference mathematical introductions to SDP are given in sections 1.2 and 2.1 of [Ber95] and [Put14], respectively.

Specification components. The specification of an SDP comprises three parts. The first part consists of four components that specify the sequential decision *process* that underlies a decision *problem*:

- A monad M , accounting for the uncertainties that affect the decision process:¹.

$$M : Type \rightarrow Type$$

- A type family X

$$X : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow Type$$

where $X\ t$ is the type of states at decision step t

- A type family Y

$$Y : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow X\ t \rightarrow Type$$

where $Y\ t\ x$ is the type of controls available at decision step t and state x

- A transition function

$$next : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow (x : X\ t) \rightarrow Y\ t\ x \rightarrow M\ (X\ (S\ t))$$

such that $next\ t\ x\ y$ is an M -structure of the states that can be reached by selecting control y in state x at decision step t .

The uncertainty monad, the states, the controls and the next function completely specify a decision process: if we were given a rule for selecting controls for a given decision process (that is, a function that gives us a control for every possible state) and an initial state (or a probability distribution of initial states) we could, in principle, compute all possible trajectories compatible with that initial state (or with that probability distribution) together with their probabilities.

Indeed, a sequential decision problem for n steps consists of finding a sequence of n *policies* (in control theory, functions that map states to controls or, in other words, decision rules, are called policies) that, for a given decision process, maximises the value of taking n decision steps according to those policies, one after the other.

In turn, the value of taking n decision steps according to a sequence of n policies is defined through a measure (in stochastic problems often the expected-value measure) of a sum of rewards obtained along the trajectories.

It follows that, in order to fully specify a decision problem, one has to define the rewards obtained at each decision step, the sum that the decision maker seeks to maximise and the measure function. This is done in terms of six problem specification components that form the second part of the specification.

- A type of values

$$Val : Type$$

¹Discussing the notion of monad here would go beyond the scope of this report, but see [Wad92] for an introduction to monads in computer science, and our papers [BBJR21] and [BB21, Appendix 1.2] for their application in the context of the Botta et al. framework.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of a stochastic SDP.

- A reward function

$$reward : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow (x : X \ t) \rightarrow Y \ t \ x \rightarrow X \ (S \ t) \rightarrow Val$$

$reward \ t \ x \ y \ x'$ is the reward obtained by selecting control y in state x when the next state is x'

- A binary operation

$$(\oplus) : Val \rightarrow Val \rightarrow Val$$

for aggregating rewards

- a reference value

$$zero : Val$$

determining an initial reward (or cost) before taking any decision²

- A measure

$$meas : M \ Val \rightarrow Val$$

- A total preorder

$$(\sqsubseteq) : Val \rightarrow Val \rightarrow Type$$

that allows to compare values.

A few remarks are at place here.

1. In many applications, Val is a numerical type and controls represent amounts of used resources like fuel, water, etc. In these cases, the reward function encodes the value (cost) of these resources (and perhaps also the benefits achieved by using them) over a decision step. Often, the latter also depend both on the "current" state x and on the next state x' .

²The name might suggest that $zero$ is supposed to be a neutral element relative to \oplus . However, this is not required by the framework.

2. When Val is a numerical type, \oplus is often the canonical addition associated with that type. However, in many applications more flexibility is needed, e.g., to model that decision makers value later rewards less than earlier ones. Again, formulating the theory in terms of a generic addition rule nicely covers all these applications.
3. Mapping $reward\ t\ x\ y$ onto $next\ t\ x\ y$ (remember that M is a monad and thus a functor) yields a value of type $M\ Val$. These are the *possible* rewards obtained by selecting control y in state x at decision step t .
4. In mathematical theories of optimal control, Val often is \mathbb{R} , M is a probability monad and the probability distributions on real numbers are compared based on the *expected value measure*. See Figure 1 for a schematic illustration of a stochastic SDP.
5. In many applications, most prominently in climate policy, measuring uncertainty of rewards in terms of expected value measures is inadequate. This is why the theory provides the possibility to use other measures (and monads) as well. However, combinations of measure, monad and \oplus need to fulfil certain compatibility conditions which will be discussed in Section 4.

The third part of a specification concerns the axioms that the data components have to fulfil. These parts are needed for the verification of the monadic backward induction algorithm which will be discussed in Section 4.

- Monad structure of M

$$monadM : Monad\ M$$

- The relation \sqsubseteq is a total preorder

$$lteTP : TotalPreorder\ (\sqsubseteq)$$

- Monotonicity axioms for \oplus and $meas$

$$\begin{aligned} plusMon & : \{v1, v2, v3, v4 : Val\} \rightarrow \\ & \quad v1 \sqsubseteq v2 \rightarrow v3 \sqsubseteq v4 \rightarrow (v1 \oplus v3) \sqsubseteq (v2 \oplus v4) \\ measMon & : Functor\ M \Rightarrow \{A : Type\} \rightarrow \\ & \quad (f, g : A \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow ((a : A) \rightarrow f\ a \sqsubseteq g\ a) \rightarrow \\ & \quad (ma : M\ A) \rightarrow meas\ (map\ f\ ma) \sqsubseteq meas\ (map\ g\ ma) \end{aligned}$$

- Compatibility conditions for M , $meas$ and \oplus :

- The measure needs to be left-inverse to $pure$:³

$$measPureSpec : Monad\ M \Rightarrow meas \circ pure \doteq id$$

- Applying the measure after $join$ needs to be extensionally equal to applying it after $map\ meas$:

$$measJoinSpec : Monad\ M \Rightarrow meas \circ join \doteq meas \circ map\ meas$$

- For arbitrary $v : Val$ and non-empty $mv : M\ Val$ applying the measure after mapping $(v \oplus)$ onto mv needs to be equal to applying $(v \oplus)$ after the measure:

$$\begin{aligned} measPlusSpec & : Monad\ M \Rightarrow (v : Val) \rightarrow (mv : M\ Val) \rightarrow (NonEmpty\ mv) \rightarrow \\ & \quad (meas \circ map\ (v \oplus))\ mv = ((v \oplus) \circ meas)\ mv \end{aligned}$$

³The symbol \doteq denotes *extensional* equality, see [BBJR21] and [BB21, Appendix 1.3].

For convenience, we may package up the above in records or type classes (called *interfaces* in Idris), so that we can work with more than one SDP instance at a time.

```
interface Monad M ⇒ MSDProcess (M : Type → Type)
  (X : (t : ℕ) → Type) (Y : (t : ℕ) → X t → Type) where
  next : (t : ℕ) → (x : X t) → Y t x → M (X (S t))
```

The definition of a monadic SDP requires the value type *Val* to carry some algebraic structure captured by more general interfaces

```
interface Pointed (T : Type) where
  point : T

interface Preorder (T : Type) where
  (≤) : T → T → Type
```

```
interface Monad M ⇒ MAlgebra (M : Type → Type) (T : Type) where
  alg : M T → T
```

The Idris standard library already has an interface for semigroups amounting to

```
interface Semigroup (T : Type) where
  (⊕) : T → T → T
```

Now we can define an interface for monadic SDPs:

```
interface (MSDProcess M X Y,
  Pointed Val, Preorder Val, Semigroup Val, MAlgebra M Val) ⇒
  MSDProblem (M : Type → Type)
  (X : (t : ℕ) → Type) (Y : (t : ℕ) → X t → Type)
  (Val : Type) where
  reward : (t : ℕ) → (x : X t) → Y t x → X (S t) → Val
```

These interfaces only encapsulate the data part of the definitions. For verification purposes we could moreover define interfaces for the axioms that have to be fulfilled. E.g. for functors (prerequisite for monads):

```
interface Functor F ⇒ VeriFunctor (F : Type → Type) where
  mapPresId   : {A : Type} → ExtEq {A = F A} (map id) id
  mapPresComp : {A, B, C : Type} → (f : A → B) → (g : B → C) →
    ExtEq {A = F A} (map (g ∘ f)) (map g ∘ map f)
  mapPresEE   : {A, B : Type} → (f, g : A → B) →
    ExtEq f g → ExtEq {A = F A} (map f) (map g)
```

For the case of functors and monads we have discussed design choices that go into the definition of such verification interfaces in [BBJR21], but in this report we will not go further into this issue.

Solution components. The second set of components of the theory is a generic formalisation of classical optimal control theory for sequential decision problems. Here, we recall the central elements. Motivation for the formalisation can be found in [BJI⁺17b], [BJI17a] and [BJI18]. For an introduction to the mathematical theory of optimal control, we recommend [Put14] and [Ber95].

The basic notion of control theory is that of a *policy* – a decision rule. Policies are functions from states to controls:

```
Policy : (t : ℕ) → Type
Policy t = (x : X t) → Y t x
```

Policy sequences of length $n : \mathbb{N}$ then are essentially just vectors of policies.⁴

⁴Note that in Idris, *S* and *Z* are the constructors of the data type of natural numbers \mathbb{N} . Arguments in curly brackets like $\{t : \mathbb{N}\}$ in the definition of *Nil* and $(::)$ are *implicit* parameters. If they can be inferred from the context, they don't have to be given as arguments later on. For $(::)$ this allow to write policy sequences composed of a policy *p* and as policy sequence *ps* simply as $p :: ps$.

data *PolicySeq* : (t : ℕ) → (n : ℕ) → Type **where**
Nil : { t : ℕ } → *PolicySeq* t Z
 (::) : { t, n : ℕ } → *Policy* t → *PolicySeq* (S t) n → *PolicySeq* t (S n)

Perhaps, the most important notion in the mathematical theory of optimal control is that of *value function*. The value function takes two arguments: a policy sequence *ps* for making *n* decision steps starting from decision step *t* and an initial state in $x : X$. It computes the value of taking *n* decision steps according to the policies *ps* when starting in *x*:

val : Functor *M* ⇒ { t, n : ℕ } → *PolicySeq* t n → X t → Val
val { t } *Nil* x = zero
val { t } (p :: ps) x = **let** y = p x **in**
 let mx' = next t x y **in**
 meas (map (reward t x y ⊕ val ps) mx')

where

(⊕) : { A : Type } → (f, g : A → Val) → A → Val
 f ⊕ g = λ a ⇒ f a ⊕ g a

is a lifted version of ⊕. Notice that, independently of the initial state *x*, the value of the empty policy sequence is *zero*, the problem-specific reference value that has to be provided as part of a problem specification.

The value of a policy sequence consisting of a first policy *p* and of a tail policy sequence *ps* is defined inductively as the measure of a *M*-structure of *Val* values. These values are obtained by first computing the control *y* dictated by *p* in *x*, the *M*-structure of possible next states *mx'* dictated by *next* and finally by adding *reward t x y x'* and *val ps x'* for all *x'* in *mx'*. The result of this functorial mapping is then measured with the problem-specific measure *meas* to obtain a result of type *Val*.

As shown in [BB21], *val ps x* does compute the *meas*-measure of the ⊕-sum of the *reward*-rewards along the possible trajectories starting at *x* under *ps* for sound choices of *meas*. We will come back to this in Section 4.

The above definition of *val* can be exploited to compute policy sequences that are provably optimal. This observation was originally made by Bellman [Bel57] for deterministic and stochastic SDPs. Provided that we can compute optimal extensions of arbitrary policy sequences

bestExt : Functor *M* ⇒ { t, n : ℕ } → *PolicySeq* (S t) n → *Policy* t

it is easy to derive a generic implementation of backward induction:⁵

bi : Functor *M* ⇒ (t : ℕ) → (n : ℕ) → *PolicySeq* t n
bi t Z = *Nil*
bi t (S n) = **let** ps = *bi* (S t) n **in** *bestExt* ps :: ps

This implementation of backward induction can be proven to compute *optimal policy sequences* if *bestExt* computes *optimal extensions* of policy sequences:

BestExt : Functor *M* ⇒ { t, n : ℕ } → *PolicySeq* (S t) n → *Policy* t → Type
BestExt { t } ps p = (p' : *Policy* t) → (x : X t) → val (p' :: ps) x ⊑ val (p :: ps) x

bestExtSpec : Functor *M* ⇒ { t, n : ℕ } → (ps : *PolicySeq* (S t) n) → *BestExt* ps (bestExt ps)

We come back to this in Section 4.

2.2 Lightweight vs. full theory

As noted in the beginning of this section, the theory proposed in [BJI17a] is slightly more general than the one presented here.

⁵Note that in control theory *backward induction* is often referred to as *the dynamic programming algorithm* where the term *dynamic programming* is used in the original sense of [Bel57].

In particular, in the lightweight theory, policies are just functions from states to controls:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Policy} &: (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{Type} \\ \text{Policy } t &= (x : X \ t) \rightarrow Y \ t \ x \end{aligned}$$

By contrast, in [BJI17a], policies are indexed over a number of decision steps n

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Policy} &: (t, n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{Type} \\ \text{Policy } t \ Z &= \text{Unit} \\ \text{Policy } t \ (S \ m) &= (x : X \ t) \rightarrow \text{Reachable } x \rightarrow \text{Viable } (S \ m) \ x \rightarrow \text{GoodCtrl } t \ x \ m \end{aligned}$$

and their domain for $n > 0$ is restricted to states that are *reachable* and *viable* for n steps. This allows to cope with states whose control set is empty and with transition functions that return empty M -structures of next states. (For a discussion of reachability and viability see [BJI17a, Sec. 3.7 and 3.8].)

This generality, however, comes at a cost: Compare e.g. the proof of Bellman’s principle in [BB21, Appendix 5] with the corresponding proof in [BJI17a, Appendix B]. The impact of the reachability and viability constraints on other parts of the theory is even more severe.

Here, we have decided to trade some generality for better readability and ease of use, opting for a lightweight version of the original theory. Still, for the generic backward induction algorithm we need to make sure that it is possible to define policy sequences of the length required for a specific SDP. This can e.g. be done by postulating controls to be non-empty:

$$\text{notEmptyY} : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow (x : X \ t) \rightarrow Y \ t \ x$$

We also impose a non-emptiness requirement on the transition function *next* that is relevant in the context of the correctness result of [BB21] (see discussion in Section 7 of the paper).

$$\text{nextNonEmpty} : \{t : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (x : X \ t) \rightarrow (y : Y \ t \ x) \rightarrow \text{NonEmpty } (\text{next } t \ x \ y)$$

Above we have not discussed under which conditions one can implement optimal extensions of arbitrary policy sequences. This is an interesting topic but not central to the purpose of the current report. For the same reason we have not addressed the question of how to make *bi* more efficient by tabulation. We briefly discuss the specification and implementation of optimal extensions in the framework in [BB21, Appendix 7]. We refer the reader interested in tabulation of *bi* to [SequentialDecisionProblems.TabBackwardsInduction](#) of [B⁺21].

3 Trajectories, flow and total rewards

In the previous section, we have seen the core components of the framework. In this section we introduce some additional infrastructure for working with sequential decision processes and problems.

State trajectories. Given a policy sequence (optimal or not) and an initial state for an SDP, we can compute the M -structure of possible trajectories starting at that state:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{data } \text{StateSeq} &: (t, n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{Type} \ \text{where} \\ \text{Nil} &: \{t : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{StateSeq } t \ Z \\ (\#) &: \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow X \ t \rightarrow \text{StateSeq } (S \ t) \ n \rightarrow \text{StateSeq } t \ (S \ n) \\ \\ \text{trjX} &: \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t \ n \rightarrow X \ t \rightarrow M \ (\text{StateSeq } t \ (S \ n)) \\ \text{trjX } \{t\} \ \text{Nil } x &= \text{pure } (x \ \# \ \text{Nil}) \\ \text{trjX } \{t\} \ (p :: ps) \ x &= \text{let } y = p \ x \ \text{in} \\ &\quad \text{let } mx' = \text{next } t \ x \ y \ \text{in} \\ &\quad \text{map } (x \ \#) \ (mx' \gg= \text{trjX } ps) \end{aligned}$$

In order to extract specific information from a state trajectory, it is helpful to have a map-like function

```

mapX : {t, n : ℕ} → {O : Type} → ({t' : ℕ} → X t' → O)
      → StateSeq t n → Vect n O
mapX obs Nil      = []
mapX obs (x # xs) = obs x :: mapX obs xs

```

Or if we explicitly need the value of t :

```

mapX' : {t, n : ℕ} → {O : Type} → ((t' : ℕ) → X t' → O)
      → StateSeq t n → Vect n O
mapX'   obs Nil      = []
mapX' {t} obs (x # xs) = obs t x :: mapX' obs xs

```

Consider a type of policy functions

```

PolicyFunction : Type
PolicyFunction = (t : ℕ) → (x : X t) → Y t x

```

that is, a policy function computes a control for any time step and state at that step. Then, omitting policy sequences, we can compute trajectories by

```

trjX' : Monad M ⇒ {t : ℕ} → PolicyFunction → (n : ℕ) → X t → M (StateSeq t (S n))
trjX'   _pol Z   x = pure (x # Nil)
trjX' {t} pol (S n) x = let y = pol t x in
                        let mx' = next t x y in
                        map (x #) (mx' >>= trjX' pol n)

```

We could also consider any finite trajectories as initial segment of an infinite one. Consider for this infinite sequences (streams) of states:

```

codata StateStream : (ℕ → Type) where
  XCons : {t : ℕ} → X t → StateStream (S t) → StateStream t

```

Then we can compute infinite trajectories (in principle though not in practice) by

```

partial
trjX_MStream : Monad M ⇒ PolicyFunction → (t : ℕ) → X t → M (Inf (StateStream t))
trjX_MStream pol t x = let y = pol t x in
                      let mx' = next t x y in
                      let mtrj = trjX_MStream pol (S t) in
                      let mapCons = map {f = M} (Delay ∘ XCons {t} x) in
                      mx' >>= (mapCons ∘ mtrj)

```

However, Idris will not certify that this function is total as the definition of $trjX_MStream$ does not meet the totality checker's syntactic guard condition for the recursive call.

For a deterministic transition function

```

step : (t : ℕ) → (x : X t) → Y t x → X (S t)

```

there is no such problem:

```

trjX_Stream : PolicyFunction → (t : ℕ) → X t → StateStream t
trjX_Stream pol t x = let y = pol t x in
                    let x' = step t x y in
                    x 'XCons' trjX_Stream pol (S t) x'

```

To recover finite trajectories, we can use a helper function

```

take : (t, n : ℕ) → Inf (StateStream t) → StateSeq t n
take _t Z   _xs = Nil
take t (S n) (XCons x xs) = x # (take (S t) n xs)

```

such that

```

trjXLemma : Monad M ⇒ (t, n : ℕ) → (pol : PolicyFunction) → (x : X t) →
  map (take t (S n)) (trjX_MStream pol t x) = trjX' pol n x

```

Flow. If we are not interested in the whole trajectory, but only in the final state, we can define a multi-step *flow* function from the single-step transition function *next*:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{flow} &: \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t \ n \rightarrow X \ t \rightarrow M \ (X \ (n + t)) \\ \text{flow } \text{Nil } x &= \text{pure } x \\ \text{flow } \{t\} \{n = S \ n\} (p :: ps) \ x &= \text{rewrite } \text{plusSuccRightSucc } n \ t \ \text{in} \\ &\quad \text{next } t \ x \ (p \ x) \gg= \text{flow } ps \end{aligned}$$

where the *plusSuccRight* $n \ t$ is the lemma $S \ (n + t) = n + S \ t$ which is required to change make the outcome type correct: The *rewrite* mechanism changes the type $M \ (X \ (S \ (n + t)))$ of $\text{next } t \ x \ (p \ x) \gg= \text{flow } ps$ (which is inferred by the Idris type checker) to the expected result type $M \ (X \ S \ (n + t))$ (which is definitionally equal⁶ to $M \ (X \ (S \ n + t))$).

More informative trajectories. Computing a “trajectory of rewards” requires more information than just a sequence of states, since rewards may depend not only on one state but also on its successor state and the control used. We therefore define more expressive trajectories

$$\begin{aligned} \text{data } \text{StateCtrlSeq} &: (t, n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{Type} \ \text{where} \\ \text{Last} &: \{t : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow X \ t \rightarrow \text{StateCtrlSeq } t \ (S \ Z) \\ (\#\#) &: \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (x : X \ t \ ** \ Y \ t \ x) \rightarrow \text{StateCtrlSeq } (S \ t) \ (S \ n) \rightarrow \text{StateCtrlSeq } t \ (S \ (S \ n)) \\ \\ \text{trj} &: \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t \ n \rightarrow X \ t \rightarrow M \ (\text{StateCtrlSeq } t \ (S \ n)) \\ \text{trj } \{t\} \ \text{Nil } x &= \text{pure } (\text{Last } x) \\ \text{trj } \{t\} \ (p :: ps) \ x &= \text{let } y = p \ x \ \text{in} \\ &\quad \text{let } mx' = \text{next } t \ x \ y \ \text{in} \\ &\quad \text{map } ((x \ ** \ y) \#\#) \ (mx' \gg= \text{trj } ps) \end{aligned}$$

where we use *StateCtrlSeq* as type of trajectories. Essentially it is a non-empty list of (dependent) state/control pairs, with the exception of the base case which is a singleton just containing the last state reached. Now we can now compute lists of rewards

$$\begin{aligned} \text{trjR} &: \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{StateCtrlSeq } t \ n \rightarrow \text{List } \text{Val} \\ \text{trjR } \{t\} \ (\text{Last } x) &= [\text{zero}] \\ \text{trjR } \{t\} \ ((x \ ** \ y) \#\# \ xys) &= \text{reward } t \ x \ y \ (\text{head } xys) :: \text{trjR } xys \end{aligned}$$

where *head* is a helper function that extracts the head of a state-control sequence

$$\begin{aligned} \text{head} &: \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{StateCtrlSeq } t \ (S \ n) \rightarrow X \ t \\ \text{head } (\text{Last } x) &= x \\ \text{head } ((x \ ** \ y) \#\# \ xys) &= x \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, we can compute the *total reward* for a single trajectory, i.e. its sum of rewards:⁷

$$\begin{aligned} \text{sumR} &: \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{StateCtrlSeq } t \ n \rightarrow \text{Val} \\ \text{sumR } \{t\} \ (\text{Last } x) &= \text{zero} \\ \text{sumR } \{t\} \ ((x \ ** \ y) \#\# \ xys) &= \text{reward } t \ x \ y \ (\text{head } xys) \oplus \text{sumR } xys \end{aligned}$$

By mapping *sumR* onto an *M*-structure of trajectories, we obtain an *M*-structure containing the individual sums of rewards of the trajectories. Now, using the measure function, we can compute the *measured total reward* for a policy sequence *ps* and an initial state *x*:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{val}' &: \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : \text{PolicySeq } t \ n) \rightarrow (x : X \ t) \rightarrow \text{Val} \\ \text{val}' \ ps &= \text{meas} \circ \text{map } \text{sumR} \circ \text{trj } ps \end{aligned}$$

The measured total reward is the generic analogue of what is called the *expected total reward* in the standard case of stochastic SDPs using the expected value measure (see [Put14, ch. 4.1.2]). This function plays a crucial role in the semantic verification of the framework that has been presented in [BB21] and will be discussed in the next section.

⁶If two expressions are *definitionally equal*, the type checker can automatically transform them into the same term and thus automatically infer that they are equal, without requiring an additional equality proof like the *plusSuccRight* lemma.

⁷More concisely *sumR* may be expressed using the *foldr* operator: $\text{sumR} = \text{foldr } (\oplus) \ \text{zero} \circ \text{trR}$.

Comparison experiments. Based on the above functions for calculating trajectories and values, further infrastructure for different kinds of comparison experiments can be defined in a straightforward manner. We give here some examples.

Given a vector of policy sequences, we can compute the vector of corresponding monadic structures of trajectories:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{trjPar} &: \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{n, m, t : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{Vect } m (\text{PolicySeq } t \ n) \rightarrow X \ t \rightarrow \\ &\quad \text{Vect } m (M (\text{StateSeq } t \ (S \ n))) \\ \text{trjPar } \text{pss } x_0 &= \text{map } (\text{flip } \text{trjX } x_0) \ \text{pss} \end{aligned}$$

or for a sequence of states (i.e. starting at increasing time steps) and a policy sequence:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{trjSeq} &: \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n, m : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (\{t' : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t' \ n) \rightarrow \\ &\quad \text{StateSeq } t \ m \rightarrow \text{Vect } m (t' : \mathbb{N} ** M (\text{StateSeq } t'' \ (S \ n))) \\ \text{trjSeq } \{t\} \ \text{ps } \text{Nil} &= [] \\ \text{trjSeq } \{t\} \ \text{ps } (x \# \text{xs}) &= (t ** \text{trjX } \text{ps } x) :: \text{trjSeq } \text{ps } \text{xs} \end{aligned}$$

A version of trjPar adding information about the initial time step to the output:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{trjPar}' &: \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n, m : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{Vect } m ((t' : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t' \ n) \rightarrow \\ &\quad X \ t \rightarrow \text{Vect } m (t : \mathbb{N} ** M (\text{StateSeq } t \ (S \ n))) \\ \text{trjPar}' \{t\} \{n\} [] &\quad x = [] \\ \text{trjPar}' \{t\} \{n\} (\text{ps} :: \text{pss}) \ x &= (t ** \text{trjX } (\text{ps } t) \ x) :: \text{trjPar}' \ \text{pss } \ x \end{aligned}$$

Compute the trajectories for a vector of policy sequences and a state sequence of initial states:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{trjParSeq} &: \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n, m, s : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{Vect } s ((t' : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t' \ n) \rightarrow \\ &\quad \text{StateSeq } t \ m \rightarrow \text{Vect } m (\text{Vect } s (t : \mathbb{N} ** M (\text{StateSeq } t \ (S \ n)))) \\ \text{trjParSeq } \text{pss } \text{xs} &= \text{mapX } (\text{trjPar}' \ \text{pss}) \ \text{xs} \end{aligned}$$

And the same for multiple state sequences of initial states:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{trjParVSeq} &: \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n, m, s, u : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \\ &\quad \text{Vect } s ((t' : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t' \ n) \rightarrow \\ &\quad \text{Vect } u (M (\text{StateSeq } t \ m)) \rightarrow \\ &\quad \text{Vect } u (M (\text{Vect } m (\text{Vect } s (t : \mathbb{N} ** M (\text{StateSeq } t \ (S \ n)))))) \\ \text{trjParVSeq } \{n\} \ \text{pss } \text{mxss} &= \text{map } (\text{map } (\text{trjParSeq } \{n\} \ \text{pss})) \ \text{mxss} \end{aligned}$$

This function may be used for a two-stage computation as indicated in Figure 2

$$\begin{aligned} \text{twoStageAssessment} &: \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n, m, u, v : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \\ &\quad (\text{pss} : \text{Vect } u (\text{PolicySeq } t \ n)) \rightarrow \\ &\quad (\text{pss}' : \text{Vect } v ((t' : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t' \ m)) \rightarrow X \ t \\ &\quad \rightarrow \text{Vect } u (M (\text{Vect } (S \ n) (\text{Vect } v (t : \mathbb{N} ** M (\text{StateSeq } t \ (S \ m)))))) \\ \text{twoStageAssessment } \{t\} \ \text{pss } \text{pss}' &= \\ \text{let } \text{stage1} &= \text{trjPar } \text{pss} \text{ in} \\ \text{let } \text{stage2} &= \text{trjParVSeq } \text{pss}' \text{ in} \\ \text{stage2} \circ \text{stage1} & \end{aligned}$$

This kind of assessment will be relevant for the notion of *lost option commitment* explored in the context of TiPES Deliverable D6.3 [MMCB22a, MMCBB22b]. If we are not interested in full (monadic) trajectories but only in the final states or the aggregated values resulting from different policy sequences, we can use the following functions:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{flowPar} &: \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n, m : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{Vect } m ((t' : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t' \ n) \rightarrow \\ &\quad X \ t \rightarrow \text{Vect } m (M (X \ (n + t))) \\ \text{flowPar } \{t\} \{n\} [] &\quad x = [] \\ \text{flowPar } \{t\} \{n\} (\text{ps} :: \text{pss}) \ x &= \text{flow } (\text{ps } t) \ x :: \text{flowPar } \text{pss } \ x \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{flowParSeq} &: \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n, m, s : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{StateSeq } t \ n \rightarrow \\ &\quad \text{Vect } s ((t' : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t' \ m) \rightarrow \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2: Two-stage parallel computation along multiple policy sequences illustrating the computation of *lost option commitment* explored in the context of TiPES Deliverable D6.3 [MMCBB22a, MMCBB22b].

$$\text{Vect } n \ (t'' \ ** \ \text{Vect } s \ (M \ (X \ (m + t''))))$$

$$\text{flowParSeq } xs \ pss = \text{mapX}' \ (\lambda t, x \Rightarrow (t \ ** \ (\text{flowPar } pss \ x))) \ xs$$

and

$$\text{valPar} : \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n, m : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{Vect } m \ ((t' : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t' \ n) \rightarrow$$

$$X \ t \rightarrow \text{Vect } m \ \text{Val}$$

$$\text{valPar } \{t\} \{n\} [] \quad x = []$$

$$\text{valPar } \{t\} \{n\} (ps :: pss) \ x = \text{val } (ps \ t) \ x :: \text{valPar } pss \ x$$

$$\text{valParSeq} : \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n, m, s : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow$$

$$\text{Vect } s \ ((t' : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t' \ m) \rightarrow$$

$$\text{StateSeq } t \ n \rightarrow \text{Vect } n \ (\text{Vect } s \ \text{Val})$$

$$\text{valParSeq } pss \ xs = \text{mapX} \ (\lambda x \Rightarrow \text{valPar } pss \ x) \ xs$$

$$\text{twoStageValuation} : \text{Monad } M \Rightarrow \{t, n, m, u, v : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow$$

$$(pss : \text{Vect } u \ (\text{PolicySeq } t \ n)) \rightarrow$$

$$(pss' : \text{Vect } v \ ((t' : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t' \ m)) \rightarrow$$

$$X \ t \rightarrow \text{Vect } u \ (M \ (\text{Vect } (S \ n) \ (\text{Vect } v \ \text{Val})))$$

$$\text{twoStageValuation } \{u\} \ pss \ pss' =$$

$$\text{let } \text{stage1} = \text{trjPar } pss \quad \text{in}$$

$$\text{let } \text{stage2} = \text{map} \ (\text{map} \ (\text{valParSeq } pss')) \ \text{in}$$

$$\text{stage2} \circ \text{stage1}$$

Based on the function introduced in this section we can describe typical experiments like sensitivity or commitment computations [BBCMM22c, Section 3+4].

Numerical simulation. As can be seen from the type of the *next* function, the basic formalism does assume that a time-discrete one step transition function is given. Although numerical simulation is not the main objective of the framework, we sketch how to arrive at a sequential decision process when starting from a ordinary differential equation (ODE) description of a parameterised and forced dynamical system.

Consider an ODE

$$\frac{dx}{dt}(t) = f(p, t, x(t))$$

where $t : \mathcal{T}$, $x : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ for some $n : \mathbb{N}$, and $p : P$ where P is a type of parameters. The function f defining the right-hand side of the ODE has the type $P \times \mathcal{T} \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$. Typically one has on the one hand constant parameters, on the other hand time-dependent forcings. In implementations, \mathbb{R} is typically represented by floating point numbers. Here we follow this common approach and do not go into formalisation of real number arithmetic.

Using slightly more general types than above, let f be encoded as a function of type

```

Time : Type
Time = Double
Rn : Type
P : Type
f : P → Time → Rn → Rn

```

Given this representation of the RHS of the ODE, the simplest way to obtain a one step function is the forward Euler method using a uniform time step $delta_t : TimeDiff$

```

TimeDiff : Type
TimeDiff = Double
delta_t : TimeDiff

```

an addition

```
add : Rn → Rn → Rn
```

and a scalar multiplication

```
smult : TimeDiff → Rn → Rn
```

```

eulerForward : { X, X', Param : Type } →
  (add : X → X' → X) → (smult : TimeDiff → X' → X') →
  (rhs : Param → Time → X → X') → TimeDiff → Param → Time → X → X
eulerForward add smult rhs dt p t x = x 'add' (dt 'smult' (rhs p t x))

```

Given a function $natToTime$ that associates decision steps with points in time

```
natToTime : ℕ → Time
```

one might thus define a deterministic sequential decision process with

```

Framework.M T = T
X _           = Rn
Y _ _        = P

```

```
next t x y = eulerForward add smult f delta_t y (natToTime t) x
```

Now, for a real application, one would of course want to do a number of improvements of the basic idea described above. Though not in the scope of the current report, especially more accurate integration methods would be important, and could be supported by a convenient DSL to derive decision processes from ODEs.

However, a shortcoming of the above that is easy to fix is the following: For a decision problem on top of such a process, one would very likely not want to associate one decision step with one integration step.

This can be easily solved by using a generic iteration function similar to the flow function defined above:

```

iter : { A : Type } → (Time → A → A) → TimeDiff → ℕ → Time → A → A
iter f dt Z t a = a
iter f dt (S n) t a = iter f dt n (t + dt) (f t a)

```

Now, if one step of next should amount to e.g. 1000 integration steps, one can define $next$ by

```

next t x y = let aux = eulerForward add smult f delta_t y in
             iter aux delta_t 1000 (natToTime t) x

```

Note that the value of the parameter is kept constant during the intermediate iterations. This is coherent with the idea of a control parameter that can only be influenced at the decision steps. However, if the control parameters are meant to represent a continuous function, this might not be the intended behaviour. In this case it seems reasonable to use some form of interpolation to recover intermediate values and make the resulting function part of the parameters of the system.

4 Correctness of the framework

An important aspect of using a dependently typed programming language is that it allows to specify and implement programs and prove their correctness with respect to the specification all in the same language.

In [BJI17a], it was formally proved that the backward induction of the full theory computes policy sequences that are optimal with respect to the value function *val* of section 2.1 which is a monadic generalisation of the Bellman equation [Bel57]. However, in the literature on stochastic SDPs this formulation of the value function is itself part of the backward induction algorithm and needs to be verified against an *objective function* or *optimisation criterion*, called the *expected total reward* in [Put14, Ch. 4.2]. For stochastic SDPs semi-formal proofs can be found in textbooks – but monadic SDPs are substantially more general than the stochastic SDPs for which these results are established. This observation raises a number of questions:

- What exactly should “correctness” mean for a solution of monadic SDPs?
- Does monadic backward induction provide correct solutions in this sense for monadic SDPs in their full generality?
- And if not, is there a class of monadic SDPs for which monadic backward induction does provide provably correct solutions?

We have addressed these questions in [BB21] and made the following contributions to answering them:

- We put forward a formal specification that monadic backward induction should meet in order to be considered “correct” as solution method for monadic SDPs. This specification uses an optimisation criterion that is a generic version of the *expected total reward* of standard control theory textbooks. In analogy, we call this criterion *measured total reward* (computed by the function *val'* defined in Section 3).
- We consider the value function underlying monadic backward induction as “correct” if it computes the *measured total reward*.
- If the value function *val* is correct in this sense, then monadic backward induction can be proven to be correct by extending the result of [BJI17a]. However, we showed in [BB21] that *val* does not compute the *measured total reward* for arbitrary monadic SDPs that only fulfil the axioms of the [BJI17a] theory.
- We therefore formulated compatibility conditions that identify a class of monadic SDPs for which *val* and thus monadic backward induction can be shown to be correct. The conditions (*measPureSpec*, *measJoinSpec* and *measPlusSpec* of Section subsection:framework:specsol) are fairly simple and allow for a neat description in category-theoretical terms using the notion of Eilenberg-Moore-algebra.
- We gave a formalised proof that monadic backward induction fulfils the correctness criterion if the conditions hold. This correctness result can be seen as a generic version of correctness results for standard backward induction like [Ber95, Prop. 1.3.1] and [Put14, Th. 4.5.1.c].

Below we will outline the two parts of the correctness proof for the lightweight theory of Section 2.1. The full proofs, discussion of the compatibility conditions and reasons why they are required can be found in [BB21]. It is worth stressing that our conditions can be useful for anyone interested in applying monadic backward induction in non-standard situations – completely independent of the BJI-framework.

4.1 Specifying correctness

By analogy to the case of stochastic SDPs treated in textbooks like [Put14], we define backward induction for monadic SDPs to be *correct* if it computes a policy sequence that results in the optimal measured total reward for any initial state. This is expressed by the following specification:

$$biOptMeasTotalReward : Monad M \Rightarrow (t, n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow OptimalPolicySeq\ val' (bi\ t\ n)$$

where *OptimalPolicySeq* is a generic optimality predicate that takes as parameters an objective function and a policy sequence. The predicate holds if the policy sequence is optimal with respect to the objective function. Above, the objective function is the measured total reward *val'*.

$$\begin{aligned} OptimalPolicySeq : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (PolicySeq\ t\ n \rightarrow X\ t \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow PolicySeq\ t\ n \rightarrow Type \\ OptimalPolicySeq\ \{t\}\ \{n\}\ f\ ps = (ps' : PolicySeq\ t\ n) \rightarrow (x : X\ t) \rightarrow f\ ps'\ x \sqsubseteq f\ ps\ x \end{aligned}$$

In [BJI17a], Botta *et al.* have shown (for the full theory) that if *M* is a monad, \sqsubseteq a total preorder and \oplus and *meas* fulfil the two monotonicity conditions *measMon* and *plusMon*, then *bi t n* yields an optimal policy sequence with respect to the value function *val* in the sense that $val\ ps'\ x \sqsubseteq val\ (bi\ t\ n)\ x$ for any policy sequence *ps'* and initial state *x*, for any *t, n* : \mathbb{N} . Or, expressed using the generic optimality predicate, that the type

$$OptimalPolicySeq\ \{t\}\ \{n\}\ val\ (bi\ t\ n)$$

is inhabited. As seen in Sec. 2.1, the function *val* measures and adds rewards incrementally. But does it always compute the measured total reward like *val'*? Modulo differences in the presentation [Put14, Theorem 4.2.1] suggests that for standard stochastic SDPs, *val* and *val'* are extensionally equal, which in turn allows the use of backward induction for solving these SDPs. Generalising, we therefore consider *val* as correct if it fulfils the specification

$$valMeasTotalReward : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : PolicySeq\ t\ n) \rightarrow (x : X\ t) \rightarrow val\ ps\ x = val'\ ps\ x$$

If this equality holds for the general monadic SDPs of the framework, we can prove the correctness of *bi* as immediate corollary of *valMeasTotalReward*. We therefore proceed as follows:

- (1.) Prove *OptimalPolicySeq val (bi t n)*: *bi* computes optimal policy sequences wrt *val*
- (2.) Prove *valMeasTotalReward*: *val* is extensionally equal to *val'*
- (3.) Deduce *biOptMeasTotalReward*: *bi* computes optimal policy sequences wrt *val'*

4.2 Optimality with respect to val

The generic implementation of backward induction of the [BJI17a] theory uses a generalisation of *Bellman's principle of optimality*. In control theory textbooks, this principle is often referred to as *Bellman's equation*. It can be suitably formulated in terms of the notion of *optimal extension*. Recall from Section 2.1 that we say that a policy *p* : *Policy t* is an optimal extension of a policy sequence *ps* : *Policy (S t) n* if it is the case that the value of *p* :: *ps* is at least as good as the value of *p'* :: *ps* for any policy *p'* and for any state *x* : *X t*:

$$\begin{aligned} BestExt : Functor M \Rightarrow \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow PolicySeq\ (S\ t)\ n \rightarrow Policy\ t \rightarrow Type \\ BestExt\ \{t\}\ ps\ p = (p' : Policy\ t) \rightarrow (x : X\ t) \rightarrow val\ (p' :: ps)\ x \sqsubseteq val\ (p :: ps)\ x \end{aligned}$$

With the notion of optimal extension in place, Bellman's principle can then be formulated as

```

Bellman : Functor M => { t, n : ℕ } →
  (ps : PolicySeq (S t) n) → OptimalPolicySeq val ps →
  (p : Policy t) → BestExt ps p →
  OptimalPolicySeq val (p :: ps)

```

In words: *extending an optimal policy sequence with an optimal extension (of that policy sequence) yields an optimal policy sequence.* Another way of expressing the same principle is to say that prefixing with optimal extensions preserves optimality.

Proving Bellman’s optimality principle is almost straightforward and crucially relies on \sqsubseteq being reflexive and transitive (remember that \sqsubseteq is a total preorder). The proof obligation is to show that

$$\text{val } (p' :: ps') x \sqsubseteq \text{val } (p :: ps) x$$

for arbitrary p' , ps' and x of suitable types. This is achieved by transitivity of \sqsubseteq on two sub proofs:

$$\text{val } (p' :: ps') x \sqsubseteq \text{val } (p' :: ps) x$$

and

$$\text{val } (p' :: ps) x \sqsubseteq \text{val } (p :: ps) x$$

The first inequality follows from the optimality of ps (the second argument of Bellman), reflexivity of \sqsubseteq and from the two *monotonicity* properties *plusMon* and *measMon* from Section 2.1:

```

plusMon : { v1, v2, v3, v4 : Val } →
  v1 ⊆ v2 → v3 ⊆ v4 → (v1 ⊕ v3) ⊆ (v2 ⊕ v4)
measMon : Functor M => { A : Type } →
  (f, g : A → Val) → ((a : A) → f a ⊆ g a) →
  (ma : M A) → meas (map f ma) ⊆ meas (map g ma)

```

The condition *measMon* is a special case of the measure monotonicity requirement originally formulated by C. Ionescu in [Ion09] in the framework of a theory of vulnerability and monadic dynamical systems. It is a natural property that, among others, the expected value measure and the worst (best) case measure do fulfil.

The second inequality directly follows from the last argument of Bellman, a proof that *BestExt ps p*. We provide a proof of *Bellman* in [BB21, Appendix 5]. As one would expect, the proof crucially depends on the recursive definition of *val* discussed above. With *Bellman* in place, we can straightforwardly prove that the generic monadic implementation of backward induction *bi* computes policy sequences that are optimal with respect to *val*. The proof is by induction on the length of the policy sequence.

For the base case, note that the empty policy sequence is optimal because any empty policy sequence will result in value *zero* and \geq is reflexive:

```

biLemmaBase : Functor M => OptimalPolicySeq val Nil
biLemmaBase Nil x = reflexive lteTP zero

```

In the step case, we apply Bellman’s principle. We thus get the following proof of optimality with respect to *val*:

```

biLemma : Functor M => (t : ℕ) → (n : ℕ) → OptimalPolicySeq val (bi t n)
biLemma t Z      = biLemmaBase -- base case
biLemma t (S n) =                -- step case
  let ps = bi (S t) n           in -- ps computed by backward induction
  let ops = biLemma (S t) n in -- induction hypothesis
  let p = bestExt ps             in -- p computed by best extension function
  let oep = bestExtSpec ps      in -- specification of best extension
  Bellman ps ops p oep          -- application of Bellman’s principle

```

4.3 Extensional equality of val and val'

Now we show that the monadic value function val based on Bellman's equation computes the measured total reward by showing that the functions val and val' are extensionally equal

$$valMeasTotalReward : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : PolicySeq\ t\ n) \rightarrow (x : X\ t) \rightarrow val'\ ps\ x = val\ ps\ x$$

The proof of $valMeasTotalReward$ is slightly more involved than the proof of $biLemma$. Therefore we will present the main part of the proof in semi-formal equational style here, while the full implementation can be found in [BB21, Appendix 2].

Inspecting the definitions of val and val' , we see that they exhibit different computational patterns: While val' first computes all possible trajectories for the given policy sequence and initial state, then computes their individual sum of rewards and finally applies the measure once, val computes its final result by adding the current reward to an intermediate outcome and applying the measure locally at each decision step. This suggests that a transformation from val' to val will essentially have to push the application of the measure into the recursive computation of the sum of rewards. The proof is carried out by induction on the structure of policy sequences. It hinges on the three compatibility conditions between the monad M , the measure $meas$ and the operation \oplus stated in Section 2.1, $measPure$, $measJoin$ and $measPlus$. These properties ensure that the objective function val' can be transformed into the more efficient val without loss of information.⁸

Lemmas. Based on the general functor and monad properties of M and the compatibility conditions, we can prove the following technical lemmas:

$$\begin{aligned} measAlgLemma & : \{A, B : Type\} \rightarrow (f : B \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow (g : A \rightarrow M\ B) \rightarrow \\ & (meas \circ map\ (meas \circ map\ f \circ g)) \doteq (meas \circ map\ f \circ join \circ map\ g) \\ headTrjLemma & : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : PolicySeq\ t\ n) \rightarrow (r : X\ t \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow \\ & (s : StateCtrlSeq\ t\ (S\ n) \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow (x : X\ t) \rightarrow \\ & (map\ (r \circ head \oplus s) \circ trj\ ps)\ x = \\ & (map\ (const\ (r\ x) \oplus s) \circ trj\ ps)\ x \\ measSumLemma & : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : PolicySeq\ t\ n) \rightarrow \\ & (r : X\ t \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow \\ & (s : StateCtrlSeq\ t\ (S\ n) \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow \\ & (meas \circ map\ (r \circ head \oplus s) \circ trj\ ps) \doteq \\ & (r \oplus meas \circ map\ s \circ trj\ ps) \end{aligned}$$

The first lemma allows us to lift and eliminate an application of the monad's $join$ operation.⁹ The second lemma says that mapping the function $head$ onto an M -structure of trajectories computed with trj results in an M -structure filled with the initial states of these trajectories. The third lemma allows us to both commute the measure into the right summand of an \oplus -sum and to perform the head/trajectory simplification. It lies at the core of the relationship between val and val' .

Main proof. With these lemmas in place, we can prove that val is extensionally equal to val' .

Let $t, n : \mathbb{N}$, $ps : PolicySeq\ t\ n$. We prove $valMeasTotalReward$ by induction on ps .

Base case. We need to show that for all $x : X\ t$, $val'\ Nil\ x = val\ Nil\ x$. The right hand side of this equation reduces to $zero$ by definition. The left hand side can be simplified to $meas\ (pure\ zero)$ since $pure$ is a natural transformation. At this point, our first condition, $measPureSpec$, comes into play: Using that $meas$ is inverse to $pure$ on the left, we can conclude that the equality holds.

In equational reasoning style: For all $x : X\ t$,

⁸Essentially, the proof consists of an algorithm that performs this transformation.

⁹This lemma is generic in the sense that it holds for arbitrary Eilenberg-Moore algebras of a monad. Here we prove it for the framework's measure $meas$, but note that in [BB21, Appendix 4.1] we prove a generic version that is then appropriately instantiated.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{valMeasTotalReward Nil } x &= \\
(\text{val}' \text{ Nil } x) &= \{ \text{by definition of } \text{val}' \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{map } \text{sumR } (\text{trj Nil } x))) &= \{ \text{by definition of } \text{trj} \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{map } \text{sumR } (\text{pure } (\text{Last } x)))) &= \{ \text{pure is a natural transformation} \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{pure } (\text{sumR } (\text{Last } x)))) &= \{ \text{by definition of } \text{sumR} \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{pure } \text{zero})) &= \{ \text{by } \text{measPureSpec} \} = \\
(\text{zero}) &= \{ \text{by definition of } \text{val} \} = \\
(\text{val Nil } x) &
\end{aligned}$$

Step case. The induction hypothesis (*IH*) is: for all $x : X$ t , $\text{val}' \text{ ps } x = \text{val } \text{ps } x$. We have to show that *IH* implies that for all $p : \text{Policy } t$ and $x : X$ t , the equality $\text{val}' (p :: \text{ps}) x = \text{val } (p :: \text{ps}) x$ holds. For brevity (and to economise on brackets), let in the following $y = p \ x$, $mx' = \text{next } t \ x \ y$, $r = \text{reward } t \ x \ y$, $\text{trjps} = \text{trj } \text{ps}$, and $\text{consxy} = ((x ** y) \#\#)$.

As in the base case, all that has to be done on the *val*-side of the equation only depends on definitional equality. However, it is more involved to bring the *val'*-side into a form in which the induction hypothesis can be applied. This is where we leverage on the lemmas proved above.

By definition and because *map* preserves composition, we know that $\text{val}' (p :: \text{ps}) x$ is equal to $(\text{meas} \circ \text{map } ((r \circ \text{head}) \oplus \text{sumR})) (mx' \gg\gg \text{trjps})$. We use the relation between the monad's *bind* and *join* to eliminate the *bind*-operator from the term. Now we can apply the first lemma from above, *measAlgLemma*, to lift and eliminate the *join* operation.

To commute the measure under the \oplus and get rid of the application of *head*, we use our third lemma, *measSumLemma*. At this point we can apply the induction hypothesis and the resulting term is equal to $\text{val } \text{ps } x$ by definition.

The more detailed equational reasoning proof:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{valMeasTotalReward } (p :: \text{ps}) \ x &= \\
(\text{val}' (p :: \text{ps}) \ x) &= \{ \text{by definition of } \text{val}' \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{map } \text{sumR } (\text{trj } (p :: \text{ps}) \ x))) &= \{ \text{by definition of } \text{trj} \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{map } \text{sumR } (\text{map } \text{consxy } (mx' \gg\gg \text{trjps})))) &= \{ \text{map preserves composition} \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{map } (\text{sumR} \circ \text{consxy}) (mx' \gg\gg \text{trjps}))) &= \{ \text{by definition of } \text{sumR} \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{map } ((r \circ \text{head}) \oplus \text{sumR}) (mx' \gg\gg \text{trjps}))) &= \{ \text{relation } \text{bind}/\text{join} \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{map } ((r \circ \text{head}) \oplus \text{sumR}) (\text{join } (\text{map } \text{trjps } mx')))) &= \{ \text{by } \text{measAlgLemma} \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{map } (\text{meas} \circ \text{map } (r \circ \text{head} \oplus \text{sumR}) \circ \text{trjps}) \ mx')) &= \{ \text{by } \text{measSumLemma} \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{map } (r \oplus \text{meas} \circ \text{map } \text{sumR} \circ \text{trjps}) \ mx')) &= \{ \text{by definition of } \text{val}' \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{map } (r \oplus \text{val}' \ \text{ps}) \ mx')) &= \{ \text{by induction hypothesis} \} = \\
(\text{meas } (\text{map } (r \oplus \text{val } \ \text{ps}) \ mx')) &= \{ \text{by definition of } \text{val} \} = \\
(\text{val } (p :: \text{ps}) \ x) &
\end{aligned}$$

□

Technical remarks. The above proof of *valMeasTotalReward* omits some technical details that may be uninteresting for a pen and paper proof, but turn out to be crucial in the setting of an intensional type theory – like Idris – where function extensionality does not hold in general. In particular, we have to postulate that the functorial *map* preserves extensional equality (see [BB21, Appendix 1.2] and [BBJR21] for details) for Idris to accept the proof. In fact, most of the reasoning proceeds by replacing functions that are mapped onto monadic values by other functions that are only extensionally equal. Using that *map* preserves extensional equality allows to carry out such proofs generically without knowledge of the concrete structure of the functor.

4.4 Concluding correctness

Using the results from above, we can now prove the correctness of monadic backward induction, namely that the policy sequences computed by *bi* are optimal with respect to the measured total reward computed by *val'*:

```

biOptMeasTotalReward : (t, n : ℕ) → OptimalPolicySeq val' (bi t n)
biOptMeasTotalReward t n ps' x =
  let vvEqL = sym (valMeasTotalReward ps' x)    in
  let vvEqR = sym (valMeasTotalReward (bi t n) x) in
  let biOpt = biOptVal t n ps' x                in
  replace vvEqR (replace vvEqL biOpt)

```

The statement *biOptMeasTotalReward* can be seen as a generic version of textbook correctness statements for backward induction as solution method for stochastic SDPs like [Ber95, prop.1.3.1] or [Put14, Theorem 4.5.1.c]. By proving *valMeasTotalReward* we have therefore extended the verification of [BJI17a] and obtained a stronger correctness result for monadic backward induction.

5 Example: A GHG emission SDP

In this section we revisit the stochastic decision process underlying the SDP discussed in [BBC⁺21]. We first describe the problem informally. Then we give a formal specification of the underlying decision process and discuss how to derive a modular definition of the transition function guided by a Bayesian network. We will come back to this example in Section 7 and extend it to a full sequential decision problem.

5.1 Informal description of the problem

Consider a GHG emissions process in which now and for a few more decades, humanity (taken here as a global decision maker) faces two options:

1. Start a “green” transition by reducing GHG emissions according to a “safe” corridor, for example, the one depicted at page 15, Figure SPM.3a of the IPCC Summary for Policymakers [Int18]
2. Delay such transition.

In other words, assume that, over the time period between two subsequent decisions (say, for concreteness, a decade), either a transition to a nearly carbonised global socio-economic system is started or nothing happens. Further, assume that, once a transition has been started, it cannot be halted or reversed by later decisions or events. We consider this oversimplified situation only for the sake of clarity, although it might well be that green transitions are in fact fast and irreversible [ODC⁺20].

Selecting to start a green transition in a specific physical, social and economic condition yields a different “new” condition at the next decision step. Let’s call one such condition a *micro-state*.

The idea is that micro-states are detailed descriptions of physical, social and economic observables. For example, a micro-state could encode values of GHG concentrations in the atmosphere, carbon mass in the ocean upper layer, global temperature deviations, frequency of extreme events, values of economic growth indicators, measures of inequality, etc. Even if we knew the “current” micro-state perfectly, the set of possible micro-states at the next decision step (say, one decade later) would still be extremely large, reflecting both the epistemic uncertainties (imperfect knowledge) about the (physical, social and economical) processes that unfold in the time between now and the next decision step and the aleatoric uncertainty [She19] of those processes.

Descriptions of decision processes explicitly based on micro-states would be both computationally intractable and, as discussed in detail in section 6, methodologically questionable. As in the the car accident example quoted at the opening of this section, we avoid these shortcomings by

considering only a small number of sets (clusters, partitions) of micro-states. These *macro-states* (in the following, just states) consist of micro-states in which:

- A green transition has been *started* or *delayed* (*S*-states, *D*-states).
- The economic wealth is *high* or *low* (*H*-states, *L*-states).
- The world is *committed* or *uncommitted* to severe CC impacts (*C*-states, *U*-states).

In other words, we only distinguish between 8 possible states: *DHU*, *DHC*, *DLU*, *DLC*, *SHU*, *SHC*, *SLU* and *SLC* where *DHU* represent micro-states in which a green transition has been *delayed*, economic wealth is *high* and the world is *uncommitted* to future severe CC impacts. Similarly for *DHC*, *DLU*, etc.

Clearly, this is a very crude simplification. But it is useful to study the impact of uncertainty on relevant climate decisions and sufficient to illustrate our approach towards measuring how much decisions matter. Also, notice that binary partitioning of micro-states is at the core of the original notion of planetary boundaries [RSN⁺09], of the topological classification proposed in [HKDM16a] and of the social dilemmas discussed in [BDLK18].

The decision process starts in *DHU*. In this state, a decision to start a green transition can lead to any of the *DHU* ... *SLC* states, albeit *with different probabilities*: the idea is that the probability of reaching states in which the green transition has been started (*S*-states) is *higher* than the probability of reaching *D*-states, in which the green transition has been delayed. Symmetrically, we assume that the decision to delay the start of a green transition in *DHU* is more likely to yield *D*-states than *S*-states.

In other words, we assume our (global, idealised) decision maker to be *effective*, but only to a certain degree. This accounts for the fact that, in practice, decisions are not always implemented, be this because global coordination is necessarily imperfect, because global players tend to be in competition and legislation tends to have large inertia or perhaps because some other global challenge (a pandemic or an economic downturn) has taken centre stage. As demonstrated in [BJI18], limited effectiveness has a significant impact on optimal GHG emissions policies. Thus, it would be inappropriate to assume that decisions are always implemented with certainty.

Another essential trait of our stylised process is that decisions to start a green transition, if implemented, are more likely to yield states with a low level of economic wealth (*L*-states) than states with high economic wealth. This assumption reflects the fact that starting a green transition requires more investments and costs than just moving to states in which most of the work towards a globally decarbonised society remains to be done.

Finally, we assume that the probability of entering states in which the world is committed to severe CC impacts is higher in states in which a green transition has not already been started as compared to states in which a green transition has been started. Also, as one would expect, delaying transitions to decarbonised economies *increases* the likelihood of entering states in which the world is committed to severe CC impacts.

Next, we give a complete formal specification of our stylised decision process.

5.2 Formal specification of the decision process

Monad. As a first step, we have to define the uncertainty monad M . As discussed in the introduction, our stylised GHG emission process is a *stochastic* process and thus M represents stochastic uncertainty:

$$\text{Framework.M} = \text{SimpleProb}$$

Here, *SimpleProb* is a finite probability monad: for an arbitrary type A , a value of type *SimpleProb* A just consists of a list of elements of type $(A, \text{Double}_{\geq 0})$ together with a proof that the sum of the seconds of such list is positive.

States and controls. Second, we have to specify the states and the controls of the process. The states informally introduced above consisted of three components: one to indicate whether a green transition had been started or not (S or D), one to represent the economy (L or H) and one to indicate whether the state is considered committed or not (U or C). Accordingly, we just define types for each of these components:

```

data SD = S | D
data LH = L | H
data UC = U | C

```

Then each informal state can be represented as a triple, e.g. DHU as (D, H, U) . Thus, we define the type of states as¹⁰

```

State : Type
State = (SD, LH, UC)
X .t = State

```

Third, we have to specify the controls of the stylised GHG emission process. Above, we said that in states in which a green transition has not already been started (that is, in D-states), the decision maker has the option of either starting or further delaying a green transition.

```

data StartDelay = Start | Delay
Y .t (D, .x2, .x3) = StartDelay

```

However, if a green transition has already been started, the decision maker has no alternatives. We formalise this idea by defining the set of controls in S-states to be a singleton:

```

Y .t (S, .x2, .x3) = Unit

```

It will be useful to have two functions that test whether a state is committed to impacts from climate change and whether the economic wealth has taken a downturn:

```

isCommitted : (t : ℕ) → X t → ℬ
isCommitted .t (.x1, .x2, U) = False
isCommitted .t (.x1, .x2, C) = True

```

```

isDisrupted : (t : ℕ) → X t → ℬ
isDisrupted .t (.x1, H, .x3) = False
isDisrupted .t (.x1, L, .x3) = True

```

That is, $isCommitted$ ($isDisrupted$) returns $True$ in C -states (L -states) and $False$ in U -states (H -states).

The next function. Finally, we have to specify the transition function of the sequential decision process. As discussed in the introduction, this is defined in terms of transition probabilities (all these probabilities are of type $Double_{\geq 0}$).

- *The probabilities of starting a green transition:*

Let's first specify the probability that a green transition is started, conditional to the decision taken by the decision maker. Let

$$p_{S|Start} : Double_{\geq 0}$$

denote the probability that a green transition is started (during the time interval between the current and the next decision step) given that the decision maker has decided to start it. For a perfectly effective decision maker, $p_{S|Start}$ would be one.

¹⁰If we do not use an argument, we indicate this by prefixing the variable name by an underscore like the variable $.t$ in the definitions of X or Y .

Let's assume a 10% chance that a decision to start a green transition fails to be implemented, perhaps because of inertia of legislation, as discussed above:

$$p_{S|Start} = 0.9$$

Consistently, the probability that a green transition is delayed even if the decision maker has chosen to start it is

$$\begin{aligned} p_{D|Start} &: Double_{\geq 0} \\ p_{D|Start} &= one - p_{S|Start} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we denote with $p_{D|Delay}$ and $p_{S|Delay}$ the probabilities that a green transition is delayed (started) given that the decision maker has decided to delay it. As a first step, we take $p_{S|Delay}$ to be equal to $p_{D|Start}$

$$\begin{aligned} p_{D|Delay} &: Double_{\geq 0} \\ p_{D|Delay} &= 0.9 \\ p_{S|Delay} &: Double_{\geq 0} \\ p_{S|Delay} &= one - p_{D|Delay} \end{aligned}$$

albeit we might want to We want to make sure that the values of $p_{S|Start}$, $p_{D|Start}$, $p_{D|Delay}$ and $p_{S|Delay}$ are consistent with the assumption (remember the informal description of our stylised GHG emission process from the introduction) that our decision maker is, up to a certain degree, effective and require them to fulfil the inequalities

$$\begin{aligned} pSpec1 &: p_{D|Start} \leq p_{S|Start} \\ pSpec2 &: p_{S|Delay} \leq p_{D|Delay} \end{aligned}$$

- *The probabilities of economic downturns:*

In the informal description of the decision process, we said that an essential trait of the decision process is that

. . . decisions to start a green transition, if implemented, are more likely to yield states with a low level of economic wealth (L -states) than states with high economic wealth. This assumption reflects the fact that starting a green transition requires more investments and costs than just moving to states in which most of the work towards a globally decarbonised society remains to be done.

We need to formulate this idea in terms of transition probabilities. Let $p_{L|S,DH}$ denote the probability of transitions to states with a low level of economic wealth (L) given that a green transition has been started (S) from delayed states (D) with a high level of economic wealth (H). Similar interpretations hold for $p_{L|S,DL}$, $p_{L|S,SH}$, $p_{L|S,SL}$ and their counterparts for the cases in which a green transition has been delayed, $p_{L|D,DH}$ and $p_{L|D,DL}$. Remember that in our decision process

. . . once a transition has been started, it cannot be halted or reversed by later decisions or events.

In terms of transition probabilities, this means that we do not need to specify $p_{L|D,SH}$ and $p_{L|D,SL}$ because the probability of transitions from S -states to D -states is zero. We encode the requirement that “decisions to start a green transition, if implemented, are more likely to yield states with a low level of economic wealth (L -states) than states with high economic wealth” by the specification

$$pSpec3 : p_{H|S,DH} \leq p_{L|S,DH}$$

Because $p_{H|S,DH} = 1 - p_{L|S,DH}$, this requires $p_{L|S,DH}$ to be greater or equal to 50%. Let's say that

$$p_{L|S,DH} = 0.7$$

We also want to express the idea that starting a green transition in a weak economy (perhaps a sub-optimal decision?) is more likely to yield a weak economy than starting a green transition in a strong economy

$$pSpec4 : p_{L|S,DH} \leq p_{L|S,DL}$$

which requires specifying a value of $p_{L|S,DL}$ between 0.7 and 1.0, say

$$p_{L|S,DL} = 0.9$$

This fixes the values of $p_{L|S,DH}$ and $p_{L|S,DL}$ for our decision process in the ranges imposed by the “semantic” constraints $pSpec3$ and $pSpec4$. We discuss how these (and other) transition probabilities would have to be estimated in a more realistic (as opposed to stylised) GHG emissions decision process in section 6.

Next, we have to specify the remaining transition probabilities $p_{L|S,SH}$, $p_{L|S,SL}$, $p_{L|D,DH}$ and $p_{L|D,DL}$. What are meaningful constraints for these? Remember that $p_{L|S,SH}$ and $p_{L|S,SL}$ represent the probabilities of transitions to low wealth states (L -states) from H and L -states, respectively, while an already started green transition is accomplished. In this situation, and again because of the inertia of economic systems, it is reasonable to assume that transitions from H -states (booming economy) to H -states are more likely than transitions from H -states to L -states and, of course, the other way round. In formulas:

$$pSpec5 : p_{L|S,SH} \leq p_{H|S,SH}$$

$$pSpec6 : p_{H|S,SL} \leq p_{L|S,SL}$$

Again, because $p_{H|S,SH} = 1 - p_{L|S,SH}$ (and $p_{H|S,SL} = 1 - p_{L|S,SL}$), this requires $p_{L|S,SH}$ and $p_{L|S,SL}$ to be below and above 50%, respectively.

In our decision process, a high value of $p_{L|S,SL}$ implies a low probability of recovering from economic downturns in states in which a transition towards a globally decarbonised society has been started or has been accomplished.

In more realistic specifications of GHG emission processes, one may want to distinguish between these two cases, or even to keep track of the time elapsed since a green transition was started and define the probability of recovering from economic downturns accordingly.

Conversely, a low value of $p_{L|S,SH}$ means high *resilience* against economic downturns in states in which a transition towards a globally decarbonised society has been started or has been accomplished. In such states, we assume a moderate likelihood of fast recovering from economic downturns:

$$p_{L|S,SL} = 0.7$$

and also a moderate resilience

$$p_{L|S,SH} = 0.3$$

Let’s turn the attention to the last two transition probabilities that need to be specified in order to complete the description of the transitions leading to economic downturns or recoveries. These are $p_{L|D,DH}$ and $p_{L|D,DL}$.

The semantics of $p_{L|D,DH}$ and $p_{L|D,DL}$ should meanwhile be clear: $p_{L|D,DH}$ represents the probability of economic downturns and $1 - p_{L|D,DL}$ the probability of recovering (from economic downturns) in states in which a green transition has not already been started. As for their counterparts discussed above, we have the semantic requirements

$$pSpec7 : p_{L|D,DH} \leq p_{H|D,DH}$$

$$pSpec8 : p_{H|D,DL} \leq p_{L|D,DL}$$

with $p_{H|D,DH} = 1 - p_{L|D,DH}$ and $p_{H|D,DL} = 1 - p_{L|D,DL}$ and thus, by the same argument as for $p_{L|S,SH}$ and $p_{L|S,SL}$, $p_{L|D,DH}$ and $p_{L|D,DL}$ below and above 50%, respectively.

How should $p_{L|D,DH}$ and $p_{L|D,DL}$ compare to $p_{L|S,SH}$ and $p_{L|S,SL}$? Is the likelihood of economic downturns in states in which a green transition has not already been started higher or lower than the likelihood of economic downturns in states in which a transition towards a globally decarbonised society has been started or has been accomplished? Realistic answers to this question are likely to depend on the decision step and on the time elapsed since the green transition has been started, see 6. As a first approximation, here we just assume that these probabilities are the same:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{L|D,DL} &= p_{L|S,SL} \\ p_{L|D,DH} &= p_{L|S,SH} \end{aligned}$$

This completes the discussion of the probabilities of economic downturns and recoveries.

- *The probabilities of commitment to severe impacts from climate change:*

The last ingredient that we need to fully specify the transition function of our decision process are the probabilities of transitions to states that are committed to severe impacts from climate change. In the introduction, we have stipulated that

... we assume that the probability of entering states in which the world is committed to future severe impacts from climate change is higher in states in which a green transition has not already been started as compared to states in which a green transition has been started.

We account for this assumption with four transition probabilities: $p_{U|S,0}$, $p_{U|D,0}$, $p_{U|S}$ and $p_{U|D}$. The first two represent the probabilities of transitions (from uncommitted states) to uncommitted states at decision step zero for the cases in which a transition to a decarbonised economy has been implemented and delayed, respectively. Similarly, $p_{U|S}$ and $p_{U|D}$ represent the probabilities of transitions from U -states to U -states at later decision steps. We take the informal specification

... delaying transitions to decarbonised economies increases the likelihood of entering states in which the world is committed to future severe impacts from climate change.

by the letter and, for the sake of simplicity, assume that the whole increase in the likelihood of entering committed states takes place during the first step of our decision process. This is a very crude assumption and we will come back to it when we discuss the results of measures of responsibility in section 7. With these premises (and keeping in mind that $p_{C|S,0} = 1 - p_{U|S,0}$, $p_{C|D,0} = 1 - p_{U|D,0}$, etc.) our informal specification translates into the constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} pSpec9 &: p_{C|S,0} \leq p_{U|S,0} \\ pSpec10 &: p_{C|S,0} \leq p_{C|D,0} \\ pSpec11 &: p_{C|S} \leq p_{U|S} \\ pSpec12 &: p_{C|S} \leq p_{C|D} \\ pSpec13 &: p_{C|D,0} \leq p_{C|D} \end{aligned}$$

For the time being, we set $p_{U|S,0}$, $p_{U|D,0}$, $p_{U|S}$ and $p_{U|D}$ to 0.9, 0.7, 0.9 and 0.3, respectively. In words, we assume a 30% chance of committing to future severe impacts from climate change if we fail to start a green transition at the first decision step. We assume this chance to increase to 70% at later decision steps. We also assume a 10% chance of severe climate change impacts if we start a green transition at the first decision step or later.

With the transition probabilities in place, we can now specify the transition function of the decision process. For illustration, we first discuss the definition of the transition function for one specific case, before we give a more compact definition based on a Bayesian network.

Recall from Section 2 that the transition function gets as inputs the decision step, the current state and the current control/decision. Consider the case at step zero in which the (initial) state is (D, H, U) and the control is *Start*, i.e. the decision is to start a green transition:

$$\text{Theory.next } Z(D, H, U) \text{ Start} = \text{mkSimpleProb}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& [((D, H, U), p_{D|Start} * p_{H|D,DH} * p_{U|D,0}), \\
& ((D, H, C), p_{D|Start} * p_{H|D,DH} * p_{C|D,0}), \\
& ((D, L, U), p_{D|Start} * p_{L|D,DH} * p_{U|D,0}), \\
& ((D, L, C), p_{D|Start} * p_{L|D,DH} * p_{C|D,0}), \\
& ((S, H, U), p_{S|Start} * p_{H|S,DH} * p_{U|S,0}), \\
& ((S, H, C), p_{S|Start} * p_{H|S,DH} * p_{C|S,0}), \\
& ((S, L, U), p_{S|Start} * p_{L|S,DH} * p_{U|S,0}), \\
& ((S, L, C), p_{S|Start} * p_{L|S,DH} * p_{C|S,0})]
\end{aligned}$$

The result of the transition is a finite probability distribution on possible next states in which the probabilities of reaching the respective states are determined in a compositional manner from the transition probabilities introduced in the previous subsection. We only comment the definition of the probability of (S, H, U) , the state in which a green transition has been started, the economy is in a wealthy state and the world is not committed to future severe impacts from climate change. The other states' probabilities can be interpreted analogously.

The probability of (S, H, U) is defined as the product of three transition probabilities: the probability that a green transition is actually implemented, given that the decision was to do so $p_{S|Start}$; the probability that the economy is in a good state (an H-state) given that a green transition has been started from an H-state $p_{H|S,DH}$; the probability of entering states that are not committed to severe impacts from climate change, again given that a transitions to a decarbonised economy has been started $p_{U|S,0}$.

Notice that $p_{C|D,0} + p_{U|D,0}$ and $p_{C|S,0} + p_{U|S,0}$ are equal to one by definition of $p_{C|D,0}$ and $p_{C|S,0}$. The same holds for $p_{H|D,DH} + p_{L|D,DH}$ and $p_{H|S,DH} + p_{L|S,DH}$ (by definition of $p_{H|D,DH}$, $p_{H|S,DH}$) and for $p_{D|Start} + p_{S|Start}$ (by definition of $p_{D|Start}$). It follows that the sum of the probabilities of *next Z DHU Start* is one, as one would expect.

It is possible to derive the probability of (S, H, U) (and of all other possible next states) given the decision to *Start* a green transition in (D, H, U)

$$p_{S|Start} * p_{H|S,DH} * p_{U|S,0}$$

rigorously if we represent our stylised decision process as a Bayesian belief network. To this end, it is useful to introduce some notation from elementary probability theory. Different textbooks adopt slightly different notations; here, we follow [Mit97] and denote the conditional probability of entering (S, H, U) given the decision to *Start* a green transition in (D, H, U) with

$$P(S, H, U \mid Start, D, H, U)$$

Thus, our obligation is to show

$$P(S, H, U \mid Start, D, H, U) = p_{S|Start} * p_{H|S,DH} * p_{U|S,0}$$

Let x_1, x_2, x_3 denote the components of the *current* state $x: X t$ and x_1', x_2', x_3' the components of the *next* state. Thus, for $x = (D, H, U)$, we have $x_1 = D$, $x_2 = H$ and $x_3 = U$. As usual, we denote a decision in x at step t with $y: Y t x$.

The *variables* $x_1, x_2, x_3, y, x_1', x_2', x_3'$ and the decision step t are associated with the *nodes* of the Bayesian network of figure 3. The *edges* of the network encode the notion of conditional dependency: the arrow between x_1 and x_2' posits that the probability of transitions to states with a low (high) economic wealth depends on whether a green transition is currently underway or has been delayed¹¹.

The conditional probability tables associated with the nodes, encode such probabilities. Thus, for example, the table associated with x_1' posits that the conditional probability of entering S-states given that the decision (variable y) was to *Start* a green transition is $p_{S|Start}$ as discussed above. Similarly, the table associated with x_2' encodes the specification that the probability of entering an

¹¹Because of the arrows between x_2 and x_1' and x_2' , such probability also depends on whether the current state of the economy is low or high and on whether a green transition gets started or not.

Figure 3: Stylised decision process as a Bayesian network.

L-state given that an S-state was entered from a current D- and H-state is $p_{L|S,DH}$ ¹².

With a Bayesian network representation of our stylised decision process in place, we can derive

$$P(S, H, U \mid Start, D, H, U) = p_{S|Start} * p_{H|S,DH} * p_{U|S,0}$$

rigorously by equational reasoning. The computation is straightforward but we spell out each single step for clarity:

$$\begin{aligned}
& P(S, H, U \mid Start, D, H, U) \\
&= \text{-- definition of } x1' \dots y \dots x3 \\
& P(x1' = S, x2' = H, x3' = U \mid y = Start, x1 = D, x2 = H, x3 = U) \\
&= \text{-- definition of conditional probability, set theory} \\
& P(x2' = H, x3' = U, x1' = S \mid y = Start, x1 = D, x2 = H, x3 = U) \\
&= \text{-- chain rule} \\
& P(x2' = H \mid x3' = U, x1' = S, y = Start, x1 = D, x2 = H, x3 = U) * \\
& P(x3' = U, x1' = S \mid y = Start, x1 = D, x2 = H, x3 = U) \\
&= \text{-- chain rule} \\
& P(x2' = H \mid x3' = U, x1' = S, y = Start, x1 = D, x2 = H, x3 = U) * \\
& P(x3' = U \mid x1' = S, y = Start, x1 = D, x2 = H, x3 = U) * \\
& P(x1' = S \mid y = Start, x1 = D, x2 = H, x3 = U) \\
&= \text{-- Bayesian network (conditional independence)} \\
& P(x2' = H \mid x1' = S, x1 = D, x2 = H) * P(x3' = U \mid x1' = S, x3 = U) * P(x1' = S \mid y = Start) \\
&= \text{-- Bayesian network (tables)} \\
& p_{H|S,DH} * p_{U|S,0} * p_{S|Start}
\end{aligned}$$

Similar derivations can be obtained, in terms of the network of Fig. 3, for the other transition probabilities that define *next* $Z(D, H, U) \text{ Start}$ and, in fact, for all the transition probabilities that define *next*. Thus, Fig. 3 can be seen as a compact representation of the transition function *next* of our stylised decision process.¹³ The conditional probability tables can be translated into probability

¹²Notice that the conditional probability table associated with $x2'$ contains an undefined value α . This is because the probability of entering L (or H) states given that a D-state was entered starting from an S-state is irrelevant: the probability of transitions from S-states to D-states is zero (remember that we have assumed that green transitions cannot be halted or reversed by later decisions), as encoded in the third row of the table associated with $x1'$.

¹³Notice that the causal networks at the core of the storyline approach [She19] are also Bayesian belief networks,

functions in a straightforward way and then be used to define the transition function *next* without having to spell out all individual cases.

We represent the three probability tables from Fig. 3 as follows:

- the probability of transitioning into an S/D-state if the decision is *Start/ Delay*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{condX1}' : \{t : \mathbb{N}\} &\rightarrow \{x : X \ t\} \rightarrow Y \ t \ x \rightarrow \text{SimpleProb } SD \\ \text{condX1}' \{x = (D, _x2, _x3)\} \text{ Start} &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(S, p_{S|Start}), (D, p_{D|Start})] \\ \text{condX1}' \{x = (D, _x2, _x3)\} \text{ Delay} &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(S, p_{S|Delay}), (D, p_{D|Delay})] \\ \text{condX1}' \{x = (S, _x2, _x3)\} () &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(S, 1.0), (D, 0.0)] \end{aligned}$$

- the probability of transitioning to an L/H-state, if the next start is an S/D-state and the current state an S/D-state with with L/H economic wealth (recall from above that α is a placeholder value for an impossible case):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{condX2}' : SD &\rightarrow SD \rightarrow LH \rightarrow \text{SimpleProb } LH \\ \text{condX2}' \ S \ D \ H &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(L, p_{L|S,DH}), (H, p_{H|S,DH})] \\ \text{condX2}' \ S \ D \ L &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(L, p_{L|S,DL}), (H, p_{H|S,DL})] \\ \text{condX2}' \ S \ S \ H &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(L, p_{L|S,SH}), (H, p_{H|S,SH})] \\ \text{condX2}' \ S \ S \ L &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(L, p_{L|S,SL}), (H, p_{H|S,SL})] \\ \text{condX2}' \ D \ D \ H &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(L, p_{L|D,DH}), (H, p_{H|D,DH})] \\ \text{condX2}' \ D \ D \ L &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(L, p_{L|D,DL}), (H, p_{H|D,DL})] \\ \text{condX2}' \ D \ S \ _x2 &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(L, \alpha), (H, (1.0 - \alpha))] \end{aligned}$$

- the probability of transitioning to an U/C-state from an S/D-state at step $n : \mathbb{N}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{condX3}' : UC &\rightarrow SD \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \text{SimpleProb } UC \\ \text{condX3}' \ U \ S \ _Z &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(U, p_{U|S,0}), (C, p_{C|S,0})] \\ \text{condX3}' \ U \ S \ _n &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(U, p_{U|S}), (C, p_{C|S})] \\ \text{condX3}' \ U \ D \ _Z &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(U, p_{U|D,0}), (C, p_{C|D,0})] \\ \text{condX3}' \ U \ D \ _n &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(U, p_{U|D}), (C, p_{C|D})] \\ \text{condX3}' \ C \ _x1 \ _n &= \text{mkSimpleProb} [(U, 0.0), (C, 1.0)] \end{aligned}$$

Based on *condX1'*, *condX2'* and *condX3'*, we can now compute the conditional probability of a possible next state.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{jointCondProb} : (t : \mathbb{N}) &\rightarrow (x : X \ t) \rightarrow (y : Y \ t \ x) \rightarrow (x : X \ (S \ t)) \rightarrow \text{Double}_{\geq 0} \\ \text{jointCondProb } t \ (x_1, x_2, x_3) \ y \ (x_1', x_2', x_3') &= \\ \text{prob } (\text{condX1}' \ y) \ x_1' * \text{prob } (\text{condX2}' \ x_1' \ x_1 \ x_2) \ x_2' * \text{prob } (\text{condX3}' \ x_3 \ x_1' \ t) \ x_3' \end{aligned}$$

where the function

$$\text{prob} : \text{Eq } A \Rightarrow \text{SimpleProb } A \rightarrow A \rightarrow \text{Double}_{\geq 0}$$

returns the probability of an outcome $a : A$ according to a probability distribution $\text{spa} : \text{SimpleProb } A$. Thus, if we return to our example from above with $(x_1, x_2, x_3) = (D, H, U)$ and $(x_1', x_2', x_3') = (S, H, U)$

$$\text{prob } (\text{condX1}' \ \text{Start}) \ S$$

is the conditional probability $P(x_1' = S \mid y = \text{Start}) = p_{S_Start}$,

$$\text{prob } (\text{condX2}' \ S \ D \ H) \ H$$

is $P(x_2' = H \mid x_1' = S, x_1 = D, x_2 = H) = p_{H_S_DH}$ and

$$\text{prob } (\text{condX3}' \ U \ S \ 0) \ U$$

is $P(x_3' = U \mid x_3 = U, x_1' = S, t = 0) = p_{U_S_0}$.

albeit without a clear-cut distinction between state and control spaces.

Collecting all of our states into a list

```
states : List State
states = [(x1, x2, x3) | x1 ← [S, D], x2 ← [L, H], x3 ← [U, C]]
```

we can then define the transition function uniformly for all inputs using list comprehension:

```
next : (t : ℕ) → (x : X t) → Y t x → M (X (S t))
```

```
next t x y =
  mkSimpleProb {prf = prf' t x y}
  [(x', p) | x' ← states,
           p ← [jointCondProb t x y x'],
           0.0 < toDouble p]
```

In standard mathematical notation, writing $jointCondProb\ t\ x\ y\ x'$ as $\pi_{t,x,y,x'}$, the list comprehension in the definition of $next\ t\ x\ y$ can be understood like a set comprehension defining a set of state-probability pairs

$$SP_{t,x,y} = \{(x', p) \mid x' \in State, p = \pi_{t,x,y,x'}, p > 0\}$$

The condition $p > 0$ ensures that states with zero probability – i.e. *impossible* next states – are not included.

6 Interlude: Realistic and stylised processes

Before continuing the technical part of the document, let us clarify the notion of *stylised* decision process. As mentioned in the introduction, this notion was originally introduced in [BJI18] to contrast the one of *realistic* decision process. This is also the sense in which it has been used in this report.

For example, in discussing the probability of economic downturns, we have argued that, in the specification of more realistic GHG emissions decision processes, one might want to distinguish between states in which a transition towards a globally decarbonised society is ongoing and states in which the transition has already been accomplished. In the case of ongoing green transitions, one may want to consider different transition probabilities, perhaps depending on the degree to which the transition has been accomplished or the time since it was started.

From this angle, more realistic essentially means a larger number of states (remember that, as discussed in the introduction, the states of a decision process typically represent sets of micro-states with the latter being detailed descriptions of physical, economic and social conditions), perhaps also of control options (for example, fast or slow green transitions) and hence more complex transition functions.

This reductionist approach towards “realism” is paradigmatic of so-called *modelling* approaches. In climate policy advice, it has lead to (integrated assessment) models of decision processes based on high-dimensional state and control spaces and a large number of model parameters [Nor18, HWFD19].

While this is popular in climate policy assessment and advice, the usage of “realistic” integrated assessment models (IAM) has also been criticised, among others, because of their poor understandability and limited predictive capability. For example, in [Pin17], it was found that very different estimates of the “right” social cost of carbon can be “obtained” by setting the values of certain IAM parameters (for example, discount factors and climate sensitivities) to specific, arbitrary but “plausible” values and Pindyck even argued that

IAM-based analyses of climate policy create a perception of knowledge and precision that is illusory and can fool policymakers into thinking that the forecasts the models generate have some kind of scientific legitimacy [Pin17].

Similar concerns and the problem that a too strong focus on *reliability* may be unsuitable for climate decision making at regional scales, have been discussed in [She19].

Another weakness of IAMs for climate policy is their strong bias towards deterministic modelling. With very few exceptions, these models assume that decisions (e.g. of starting a global green transition) are implemented with certainty, that crucial parameterizations of climate processes (like the *equilibrium climate sensitivity*) can be estimated accurately and that the costs and the benefits of future climate changes can be accounted for in suitable “terminal” (salvage, scrap, see [Put14] section 2.1.3) rewards.

Is there a way of specifying decision processes that are useful for pragmatic climate decision making and that avoid the drawbacks of deterministic modelling approaches based on high-dimensional state spaces?

We believe that this is the case and that, rather than neglecting uncertainty, the way to address this challenge is to 0) specify low-dimensional state and control spaces that are logically consistent with the informal description of the specific decision process at stake; 1) explicitly account for the uncertainties that are known to affect best decisions for that process, 2) exploit the knowledge available (from past experience, data, model simulation, etc.) to specify trustable transition probabilities with interpretations that are consistent with that process.

This is the essence of the approach that we have demonstrated in the previous section: starting from an informal description, we have introduced formal specifications of state and control spaces that are logically consistent with that description. We have accounted for the uncertainties of the informal description in terms of twelve transition probability parameters. For each parameter, we have provided an interpretation together with a range of values compatible with that interpretation. Within these ranges, we have then chosen certain values and defined the transition function in terms of those values. For example, we have postulated a 10% chance that a decision to start a green transition fails to be implemented.

In a (more) realistic specification, this figure could perhaps have been obtained by asking a pool of experts, perhaps political scientists, historians, etc. Similarly, in more realistic specifications, the probabilities of recovering from economic downturns might be obtained from climate economists. These, in turn, might rely on model simulations, expert elicitation or perhaps statistical data. Finally, climate models (general circulation models, intermediate complexity models, low-dimensional systems of ordinary differential equations representing global mass and energy budgets) might be applied to representative micro-states samples of a given (macro) state (for example, our initial state *DHU*) to compute more realistic estimates (for example via Monte Carlo simulations) of transition probabilities, for instance, to committed states.

From this angle, the approach of “stylised” decision processes is similar to the *storyline* approach – the “identification of physically self-consistent, plausible pathways” – proposed in [She19]. The focus, there on physical consistency and causal networks, is here on logical consistency and decision networks. Common to both approaches is the need to integrate contributions from very different disciplines, ranging from theoretical computer science to the social sciences [She19, SMV⁺21].

In this enterprise, the theory of section 2 and the language extensions discussed in this report play a twofold role. On the one hand, they help ensuring that results of model simulations, expert opinions, and statistical data are applied consistently. On the other hand, they make it possible to reason about pragmatic decision processes in a formal and rigorous way.

7 Generic responsibility measures

In [BBC⁺21] we introduced generic responsibility measures to answer the following questions:

- What does it mean precisely for decisions to matter?
- Are there general ways to measure how much decisions matter when these have to be taken under uncertainty?
- Is there a natural way of comparing similar decisions at different times?

To define a notion of responsibility we use and extend the basic theory for monadic SDPs as follows:

- (S1) The *reward* function of the SDP is defined based on a specific *goal* of decision making. For example, a formal expression of “*avoiding states committed to severe climate change impacts*”.
- (S2) Verified “best” and “conditional worst” decisions are compared at the specific state at which we want to measure how much decisions matter for the goal encoded in (S1).
- (S3) We define a degree of responsibility consistent with this measure.

In [BvH18] three conditions are put forward under which “a person can be ascribed responsibility for a given outcome”:

- (C1) *avoidance*: it is possible for the person to avoid an performing an action that contributes to the outcome,
- (C2) *agency*: having the capability to act intentionally, to plan, and to distinguish between desirable and undesirable outcomes, and
- (C3) *causal relevance*: there is a causal relation between the person’s action and the outcome.

The notion of causality is not uncontroversial [Car95] and its role in formalizations of responsibility has been addressed, among others by [CH04, Hal06] and [Hal14]. Below we show that at least for sequential decision processes it is possible to define “meaningful” measures of how much decisions matter without having to deal with causality. We also discuss the relation between these measures and responsibility measures.

7.1 Illustration of the approach

For concreteness, we illustrate (S1)-(S3) for the decision problem of section 5. The extensions of the theory discussed in this section, however, are fully generic and can be applied to arbitrary decision processes. We tackle step one by first discussing conditions under which decisions shall not matter.

(S1)a: When decisions shall not matter. Consider the problem of attributing a non-negative number to the states of a decision process P :

$$mMeas : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow X \ t \rightarrow Double_{\geq 0}$$

The idea is that $mMeas \ P \ t \ x$ represents how much decisions in state x do matter: the larger, the more decisions in x matter. For the time being, assume that $mMeas \ t \ x$ takes values between zero and one. Under which conditions shall we require it to be zero? First and foremost we would like $mMeas \ t \ x$ to be zero whenever only one option is available to the decision maker in x :

$$mMeasSpec1 : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow (x : X \ t) \rightarrow Singleton \ (Y \ t \ x) \rightarrow mMeas \ t \ x = zero$$

Here, we have formalised the condition that only one option is available to the decision maker in x with the predicate $Singleton \ (Ctrl \ P \ t \ x)$.

The specification $mMeasSpec1$ is consistent with *avoidance*, one of the three conditions of [BvH18] listed above.

(S1)b: Encoding goals of decision making. To measure how much decisions matter, we have to extend a decision process to a decision problem by providing the definitions of *Val*, *reward*, *meas*, \oplus , \sqsubseteq and *zero*. In the following, we define these components for our stylised decision process of Section 5. In our example, we have a stochastic SDP for which the type and structure used for valuation are simply

$$\begin{aligned} Val &= Double_{\geq 0} \\ (\oplus) &= (+) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} zero &= 0.0 \\ (\sqsubseteq) &= (\leq) \end{aligned}$$

Here, we follow standard decision theory and take *meas* to be the expected value measure, although other measures might be used as long as they fulfil the compatibility conditions stated in Section 2.

$$meas = expectedValue$$

As a starting point for the definition of the reward function, we identify the *goal* for which we seek responsibility measures. In short, we have to say *for what* we want to measure how much decisions matter. For example, we might be interested in measuring how much decisions matter for *avoiding states that are committed to severe impacts from climate change*. Or perhaps we want to measure how much decisions matter for *avoiding climate change impacts but also economic downturns*. Formally, we may express these goals using the test functions *isCommitted* and *isDisrupted* which we defined in Section 5.

$$goal : \{t : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (X \ t) \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$$

with

$$goal \ \{t\} \ x = isCommitted \ t \ x$$

or

$$goal \ \{t\} \ x = isCommitted \ t \ x \vee isDisrupted \ t \ x$$

Then we can define the reward function in terms of this goal:

$$reward \ t \ x \ y \ x' = \mathbf{if} \ goal \ \{t = S \ t\} \ x' \ \mathbf{then} \ 0.0 \ \mathbf{else} \ 1.0$$

In the following, we will use the second definition of *goal*. In Section 7.2 below, we discuss generic goal functions and show how to pre-define *Val*, *reward*, etc. based on such functions.

(S2): Measuring how much decisions matter. With a goal encoded via the reward function, we can tackle the problem of measuring how much decisions in a state do matter for that goal.

For concreteness, let's consider the initial state (D, H, U) of our decision problem. In this state, the decision maker has two options: start a green transition or further delay it. Remember that our decision maker is effective only to a certain extent. As shown in figure 3, a decision to start a green transition may well yield a next state in which the transition has been delayed. According to Section 5, the probability of this event is $p_{D|Start}$, that is, 10%.

What does this uncertainty imply for the decision to be taken in the initial state (D, H, U) ? Answering this question rigorously requires fixing a decision *horizon*. This is the number of decision steps of our decision process that we look ahead in order to measure how much decisions matter. Remember from section 2 that the value of taking zero decision steps is always *zero*: *Val*, a problem-specific reference value that holds for every decision step and state at that step. Thus, if we look forward zero steps, no decision matters, independently of the decision step and state. But, for a strictly positive number of decision steps, we can formulate and rigorously answer the following two questions

- Is it better, in (D, H, U) to (decide to) start or to delay a green transition?
- How much does this decision matter (for avoiding climate change impacts but also economic downturns)?

To do so, we first apply the generic backward induction from Section 2 and compute an optimal sequence of policies *ps* over the horizon. Recall from Section 2 that *bi* computes provably optimal policy sequences¹⁴. This means that no other policy sequence entails better decisions than *ps* (here for the goal of avoiding climate change impacts but also economic downturns).

¹⁴If \sqsubseteq , \oplus , *meas*, etc. fulfil the specifications from Section 2.

Thus, we can compute a best decision and the value (of the sum of the rewards) over a horizon of n steps for arbitrary states:

```

best : (t, n : ℕ) → X t → String
best t Z x = "The horizon must be greater than zero!"
best t (S m) x =
  let ps = bi (S t) m in
  let p = bestExt ps in
  let b = p x in
  let vb = val (p :: ps) x in
  "Horizon, best, value: " ++
  show (S m) ++ ", " ++
  showY b ++ ", " ++
  show vb

```

What is a best decision in (D, H, U) for a horizon of only one step?

```

* Responsibility > : exec best 0 1 (D, H, U)
Horizon, best, value : 1, Delay, 0.468

```

This is not very surprising: according to the definition of *next*, the probability of entering states that are either economically disrupted or committed to severe impacts from climate change is 0.708. Thus, the expected value of deciding to start a green transition is only

$$1 - 0.708 = 0.292$$

By contrast, the expected value of deciding to delay a green transition is 0.468, as seen above. As it turns out, one has to look forward at least over three decision steps (or, in our interpretation, about three decades) for the decision to start a green transition to become a best decision in (D, H, U) . We can apply the computation

```

bests : (t : ℕ) → List ℕ → X t → IO ()
bests t Nil x = putStrLn "done!"
bests t (n :: ns) x = do putStrLn (best t n x)
                      bests t ns x

```

to study how best decisions vary with the horizon. Again, for $x = (D, H, U)$ one obtains:

```

* Responsibility > : exec bests 0 [1..8] (D, H, U)
Horizon, best, value : 1, Delay, 0.468
Horizon, best, value : 2, Delay, 0.635454
Horizon, best, value : 3, Start, 0.940669612
Horizon, best, value : 4, Start, 1.250012318344
Horizon, best, value : 5, Start, 1.533635393558128
Horizon, best, value : 6, Start, 1.790773853744118
Horizon, best, value : 7, Start, 2.0228744449805313

```

As anticipated, the decision to start a green transition at the first decision step becomes a best decision for horizons of three or more decisions. The other way round: our decision maker would have to be very myopic (or, equivalently very much discount future benefits) to conclude that delaying a green transition is a best decision in (D, H, U) .

But how much does this decision actually matter? To answer this question, we need to compare a best decision in (D, H, U) for a given time horizon to a worst decision. Again, for concreteness, let's for the moment fix the horizon to 7 decision steps.

What is the value (again, in terms of the sum of the rewards associated with avoiding climate change impacts and economic downturns) of deciding to delay a green transition in (D, H, U) ? There are different ways of answering this question, but a canonical one¹⁵ is to consider the consequences of deciding to delay a green transition at the first decision step in (D, H, U) and take later decisions

¹⁵We discuss alternative approaches in section 7.3.

optimally. In our specific problem, this corresponds to assuming that future generations will do their best to avoid negative impacts from climate change and economic downturns.

If we denote our optimal policy sequence for an horizon of 7 steps by ps , we can compute the consequences of deciding to delay at the first decision step in (D, H, U) and then take later decisions optimally by replacing the first policy of ps with one that recommends *Delay* in (D, H, U) :

```
ps : PolicySeq 0 7
ps = bi 0 7
```

```
ps' : PolicySeq 0 7
ps' = (setInTo (head ps) (D, H, U) Delay) :: tail ps
```

The function *setInTo* in the definition of ps' is a higher-order primitive: it takes a function (in this case the first policy of ps), a value in its domain and one in its codomain, and returns a function of the same type that fulfils the specification

$$(\text{setInTo } f \ a \ b) \ a = b \ \wedge \ \text{Not } (a = a') \rightarrow (\text{setInTo } f \ a \ b) \ a' = f \ a'$$

for all f , a , a' and b of appropriate type. With ps' , we can compute the value of deciding to delay a green transition at the first decision step in (D, H, U) :

```
* Responsibility > : exec show [val ps (D, H, U), val ps' (D, H, U)]
" [2.022874449805313, 1.672795254555656] "
```

The difference between the value of ps and the value of ps' in (D, H, U) then *is a measure of how much decisions in (D, H, U) matter for avoiding climate change impacts and economic downturns over a time horizon of 7 decision steps*: the bigger this difference, the more the decision matters.

S3: Responsibility measures We have argued that the difference between the value of ps and the value of ps' in (D, H, U) , is a measure of how much decisions in (D, H, U) matter for avoiding climate change impacts and economic downturns over a time horizon of 7 decision steps. This argument is justified because:

- We have defined optimal policy sequences to be policy sequences that avoid (as well as it gets) climate change impacts and economic downturns in (S1).
- Over 7 decision steps, ps is a *verified optimal* policy sequence.
- The best decision in (D, H, U) is to start a green transition:

```
* Responsibility > : exec show (head ps (D, H, U))
"Start"
```

- ps' is a sequence of policies identical to ps except for recommending *Delay* instead of *Start* in (D, H, U) and for the first decision step:

```
* Responsibility > : exec show (head ps' (D, H, U))
"Delay"
```

These facts are sufficient to guarantee that the difference between the value of ps and the value of ps' in (D, H, U) is actually the difference between the value (with respect to *goal*) of the best and of the worst decisions that can be taken in (D, H, U) .

The computation and the definitions of ps and ps' suggest a refinement and an implementation of the measure of how much decisions matter $mMeas$ put forward in the beginning of this section. First, we want $mMeas$ to depend on a time horizon n . Second, for the sake of simplicity, we want $mMeas$ to return plain double precision floating point numbers:

```
mMeas : (t : ℕ) → (n : ℕ) → X t → Double
mMeas t Z x = 0.0
```

```

mMeas t (S m) x = let ps = bi (S t) m in
  let v = toDouble (val (bestExt ps :: ps) x) in
  let v' = toDouble (val (worstExt ps :: ps) x) in
  v - v'

```

Remember that, in (S1), we have encoded the goal of avoiding severe climate change impacts and economic downturns for which we compute *mMeas* through a function

```

reward t x y : X (S t) → Double≥0

```

that returns 0 for next states that are committed to severe climate change impacts and economically disrupted and 1 otherwise. In this formulation, the value 1 is completely arbitrary: it could be replaced by any other positive number and perhaps discounted. This suggests that measures of how much decisions matter should be normalised

```

mMeas : (t : ℕ) → (n : ℕ) → X t → Double
mMeas t Z x = 0.0
mMeas t (S m) x = let ps = bi (S t) m in
  let v = toDouble (val (bestExt ps :: ps) x) in
  let v' = toDouble (val (worstExt ps :: ps) x) in
  if v == 0 then 0 else (v - v') / v

```

Notice that, in states in which the control set is a singleton, any policy has to return the same control. In particular, the best extension and the worst extension of any policy sequence have to return the same control. Therefore, *mMeas* fulfils the avoidance condition of [BvH18] *per construction*. As a consequence, in *S*-states, the measure is always 0, independently of the time horizon:

```

* Responsibility > : exec show (mMeas 0 4 (S, H, U))
"0"

```

```

* Responsibility > : exec show (mMeas 0 6 (S, L, C))
"0"

```

Notice also that *mMeas* can be applied to estimate how much decisions matter at later steps of a decision process. For example, we can assess that, for our decision process and under a fixed time horizon, decisions in (*D*, *H*, *U*) at decision step 0 matter less than decisions in (*D*, *H*, *U*) at later steps:

```

* Responsibility > : exec show (mMeas 0 7 (D, H, U))
"0.1730602684132721"

```

```

* Responsibility > : exec show (mMeas 1 7 (D, H, U))
"0.5673067719100584"

```

```

* Responsibility > : exec show (mMeas 3 7 (D, H, U))
"0.5673067719100584"

```

This is not surprising given that the best decision, in (*D*, *H*, *U*) and for a time horizon of 7 decision steps, is to start a green transition and that, as stipulated in the introduction and specified in Section 5 through

```

pSpec9 : pC | D, 0 ≤ pC | D

```

the probability of entering states in which the world is committed to future severe impacts from climate change is higher in states in which a green transition has not already been started as compared to states in which a green transition has been started.

Wrap up. Following (S1), (S2) and (S3), we have introduced a measure of how much decisions under uncertainty matter that fulfils the requirements for responsibility measures put forward in the beginning of this section.

It accounts for all the knowledge which is encoded in the specification of a decision process, it is defined uniformly for any goal a (real or hypothetical) decision maker may pursue and it is *fair* in the sense that all decisions (decision makers) are measured in the same way.

Thus, we introduce *mMeas* as a first example of responsibility measure. In the next section, we generalise it by introducing a small DSL for the specification of goals of sequential decision processes under uncertainty and discuss alternative definitions.

7.2 A syntax for defining goals

Above we have defined the reward function in terms of a function

$$goal : \{t : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (X \ t) \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$$

as

$$reward \ t \ x \ y \ x' = \mathbf{if} \ goal \ \{t = S \ t\} \ x' \ \mathbf{then} \ 0.0 \ \mathbf{else} \ 1.0$$

In [BBC⁺21], we have defined a first simple DSL for the modular definition of such goals, allowing to put forward the goal of decision making in a transparent way. Using this syntax, the goal from above could be expressed as

$$goal = Avoid \ isCommitted \ \&\& \ Avoid \ isDisrupted$$

Here *Avoid* is a function that maps Boolean predicates to goals. It is one of the constructors of the abstract syntax

```

data Goal : Type where
  Exit   : Region → Goal
  Enter  : Region → Goal
  StayIn : Region → Goal
  Avoid  : Region → Goal
  (&&)   : Goal → Goal → Goal
  (||)   : Goal → Goal → Goal
  Not    : Goal → Goal

```

to specify goals for decision processes that are informed by notions of sustainable development or management [HKDM16b, Int18]: such goals are typically phrased in terms of a verb (*avoid*, *exit*, *enter*, *stay within*, etc.) and of a *region* (predicate, subset of states) that encode notions of planetary boundaries or operational safety¹⁶.

In our formalisation, such regions are encoded by

```

Region : Type
Region = (t : ℕ) → Subset (X t)

```

where *Subset* *A* is an alias for $A \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$:

```

Subset : Type → Type
Subset A = A → ℬ

```

Such regions might e.g. be assigned according to information obtained in commitment or tipping point computations with physical models (this will be further explored in TiPES D6.3, see also [MMCBB22b, MMCBB22a]).

The syntax allows moreover to combine goals with logical operators. Given the input of the framework's reward function (the current and successor states as well as the current control) and a goal, an evaluation function then assigns a semantic to the syntactic goal expression. The result of the evaluation is a Boolean value, indicating whether the goal is attained or not. The generic reward function simply does a case split on this Boolean value and returns a reward of 0 or 1.

¹⁶for example, in [HKDM16b], a partitioning of the state space into a *sunny* region and its *dark* complement is the starting point for the construction of a hierarchy of regions: shelters, glades, lakes, trenches and abysses, see figure 1 at page 7.

```

eval : Goal → (t : ℕ) → (x : X t) → Y t x → X (S t) → ℤ
eval (Exit r)   t x y x' = let t' = S t in elem t x (r t)    ∧ ¬ (elem t' x' (r t'))
eval (Enter r)  t x y x' = let t' = S t in ¬ (elem t x (r t)) ∧ elem t' x' (r t')
eval (StayIn r) t x y x' = let t' = S t in                      elem t' x' (r t')
eval (Avoid r)  t x y x' = let t' = S t in                      ¬ (elem t' x' (r t'))
eval (g && g')   t x y x' = eval g t x y x' ∧ eval g' t x y x'
eval (g || g')   t x y x' = eval g t x y x' ∨ eval g' t x y x'
eval (Not g)    t x y x' = ¬ (eval g t x y x')

```

While the definition of *eval* is almost straightforward, domain experts do not need to be concerned with it. They just apply the constructors of *Goal* to specify the goal of decision making like in the definition of *goal* given above. The goal for which we measure how much decisions matter is then fully transparent and the rewards are computed by a generic function based on *eval goal*:

```

goal : Goal
reward t x y x' = if eval goal t x y x'
  then 1.0
  else 0.0

```

In more realistic (as opposed to stylised, see section 6) GHG emissions decision processes, states are not necessarily either fully committed or fully uncommitted to severe impacts from climate change and decision makers are confronted with many degrees of commitment, possibly infinitely many.

A similar situation holds for other predicates on states, like being *vulnerable* (or *adapted*) to climate change or for measures of economic growth or welfare. This raises the question of how to specify the goals of decision making in decision processes in which predicates like *isCommitted* do not return Boolean values but, for example, values in $[0, 1]$. In this situation, a partitioning of the state space into regions is not immediately available and the specification of goals requires an extension both of the syntax *Goal* for encoding goals and of the interpretation function *eval* associated with this syntax.

Another possibility to generalise the simple DSL from above is to allow assigning weights to each atomic goal, likewise yielding rewards in the unit interval instead of just Boolean values:

```

UnitInterval : Type
UnitInterval = (d : Double ** So (0 ≤ d ∧ d ≤ 1))
castBD : ℤ → Double
castBD True = 1.0
castBD False = 0.0

```

```

data Goal : Type where
  Exit   : UnitInterval → Region → Goal
  Enter  : UnitInterval → Region → Goal
  StayIn : UnitInterval → Region → Goal
  Avoid  : UnitInterval → Region → Goal
  (&&)   : Goal → Goal → Goal
  (||)   : Goal → Goal → Goal
  Not    : Goal → Goal

```

```

eval : Goal → (t : ℕ) → (x : X t) → Y t x → X (S t) → Double -- better: UnitInterval
eval (Exit w r)   t x y x' = let t' = S t in
  fst w * castBD (elem t x (r t) ∧ ¬ (elem t' x' (r t')))
eval (Enter w r)  t x y x' = let t' = S t in
  fst w * castBD (¬ (elem t x (r t)) ∧ elem t' x' (r t'))
eval (StayIn w r) t x y x' = let t' = S t in fst w * castBD (elem t' x' (r t'))
eval (Avoid w r)  t x y x' = let t' = S t in fst w * castBD (¬ (elem t' x' (r t')))
eval (g && g')    t x y x' = min (eval g t x y x') (eval g' t x y x')
eval (g || g')    t x y x' = max (eval g t x y x') (eval g' t x y x')
eval (Not g)      t x y x' = 1 - eval g t x y x'

```

Not that the interpretation of the logical connectives is common for fuzzy logic [Zad75]. However, one might also want to explore the individual values for multiple goals at the same time without aggregating them.

```

w1 : UnitInterval
w1 = (0.4 ** Oh)

w2 : UnitInterval
w2 = (0.3 ** Oh)

goal : Goal
goal = Avoid w1 isCommitted && Avoid w2 isDisrupted

reward t x y x' =
  if eval goal t x y x' then 1.0 else 0.0

```

Recall the function *trjR* of Section 3

```
trjR : { t, n : ℕ } → StateCtrlSeq t n → List Val
```

that computes a list with the rewards at each step. It is useful suitable for exploring the local fulfilment of goals. For such an exploration, it might be useful to preserve the information about the outcomes of multiple goals. We can implement this vectors of goals and vectors of doubles as type of values, instead of defining the reward function in terms of one single goal and resulting number:

```

dim : ℕ
goals : Vect dim Goal

Val = Vect dim Double
reward t x y x' = map (λg ⇒ eval g t x y x') goals

```

Note that in order to compare such multi-goal rewards (for optimisation), they have to either be aggregated in some way or the comparison is performed according to a priority order on the components.

7.3 Some caveats

With *mMeas* defined as in section 7 and with *goal* : *Goal* specified as above, one can recover the results for the decision process of section 5. To wrap up, let us discuss a few aspects of the responsibility measures considered so far.

One important trait of these measures is that they are obtained by extending the decision process for which one wants to measure how much decisions matter to a fully specified finite horizon sequential decision problem. In comparison to approaches like those proposed in [Hal06], [CH04] and, more recently, [HH20], this approach has both advantages and disadvantages.

From the conceptual point of view, the major advantages are simplicity and straightforwardness: in contrast to models of causality like those put forward in the works mentioned above, finite horizon sequential decision problems are conceptually simple and well understood. Also, for finite horizon sequential decision problems, we can compute *provably* best and worst policies. This guarantees that the results obtained for a specific problem are a logical consequence of the assumptions made for that problem and not of programming errors or numerical errors. Because all the assumptions underlying a specific problem are put forward explicitly via specifications like

```
goal = Avoid isCommitted && Avoid isDisrupted,
```

the approach also guarantees high standards of transparency. Simplicity and straightforwardness are also the main drawbacks of our approach: we can only derive responsibility measures for decision processes that can be naturally extended to finite horizon sequential decision problems.

This is the case for the stylised GHG emissions decision process discussed throughout our work and, indeed, for many interesting problems in climate policy because, as pointed out in [Web08]:

Climate policy decisions are necessarily sequential decisions over time under uncertainty, given the magnitude of uncertainty in both economic and scientific processes, the decades-to-centuries time scale of the phenomenon, and the ability to reduce uncertainty and revise decisions along the way.

But it is not immediately obvious how our approach could be applied to measure how much decisions matter in situations in which collective decisions emerge from a potentially large number of individual decisions, e.g., mediated through certain widely accepted mechanisms like majoritarian rules like in voting processes.

Another important aspect of the measures of responsibility proposed in this work is the comparison between verified best and what we called “conditional worst” decisions at the specific state at which we want to measure responsibility. Remember that, in the definition of $mMeas$, v and v' are $val (bestExt ps :: ps) x$ and $val (worstExt ps :: ps) x$, respectively. Here, $x : X t$ is a state at decision step t , ps is a verified optimal sequence of policies for taking n decisions starting from step $t + 1$ and $n + 1$ is the decision horizon.

Due to the definition of $bestExt$, generic backward induction and the correctness proof from section 4, $bestExt ps :: ps$ is an optimal policy sequence and $bestExt ps$ is an optimal policy (a function from states to controls) at decision step t . Similarly $worstExt ps$ is a policy that guarantees

$$val (worstExt ps :: ps) x \sqsubseteq val (p :: ps) x$$

for all $x : X t$ and $p : Policy t$. In other words, we compare “best” decision (given by $bestExt ps$) and “worst” decision (given by $worstExt ps$) in x conditional to future decisions being best ones. This is crucial because the difference between best and worst decisions (and hence our estimates of how much decisions matter) at a given step and in a give state would in general be different if we assumed that future decision are not taken optimally.

In the context of our decision problem, for example, we would come up with a different measure of responsibility for “current” decisions if we assumed that future generations do not care about avoiding negative impacts from climate change or economic downturns or, equivalently, that they do care but do not act accordingly. If there are reasons to believe that this is the case, the verified optimal policy sequence ps in the definition of $mMeas$ has to be replaced with one which is consistent with such a belief. For example, if we believe that the next generation will act more myopically (or more farsighted) than for a horizon of n decision steps, we have to compute ps accordingly.

Finally, we want to flag the role of the measure of uncertainty $meas$ from section 2 in the definition of val and thus of v and v' . In all computations shown in this section, we have taken $meas$ to be the *expected value measure* but other measures of uncertainty are conceivable and we refer interested readers to [Ion09, BJI17a] and [BB21].

8 Conclusion

We have developed domain-specific language elements for the study of dynamical systems and specification of SDP in the context of tipping point research. For better usability, we have implemented these language elements on top of a lightweight version of the original Botta et al. framework of [BJI17a]. We have defined generic measures of responsibility and a syntax to transparently express goals of decision making. We have illustrated the usage of the framework by specifying a conceptual stochastic green house gas emission problem. Furthermore, we have shown the correctness of the generic backward induction algorithm implemented in the framework in a more general setting than commonly considered in control theory. Considering that the aim of the current work is to improve accountability in the context of climate policy, this correctness result fills an important gap that had been overlooked in the previously existing verification result for the Botta et al. framework.

Nevertheless, many extensions to the work presented in this report are conceivable. Possible future work includes the following:

- Defining a syntax for systematic construction of transition functions from conditional probability functions, possibly following the approach of [Jac15, JZ20]

- Extending the language for value judgements (e.g. iterated notions of avoidance, reachability etc.), possibly following ideas for the topological classification of state spaces of [HKDM16b]
- Developing the algebraic theory of SDPs to improve modularity in the description of problems, extending work started in [KJ19].
- Incorporating notions for multi-objective / multi-stakeholder valuation for SDPs, following the risk-opportunity-analysis paradigm discussed in [MSV⁺20]
- Adding language elements for the description of problems with early warning signals (EWS) [BBCMM22c]

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Conflicts of Interest

None.

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